

WILLINGNESS TO PAY FOR RECYCLED PLASTIC

Measuring the Influence of Intergenerational Differences and Product Category Perceptions
on the stated Value for Products made from Recycled and Ocean Plastic

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Abstract

In recent years literature recognized that recycled plastic products can mitigate the plastic crisis and contribute to the development of a circular material flow. However, current research fails to assess acceptance and perceived value amongst consumers, especially in regard to differences between conventional recycled and ocean plastic. In applying the theory of planned behaviour (TPB) in combination with relevant pro-circular variables, this study defines the contrast of willingness to pay (WTP) for recycled and ocean plastic products between three generational cohorts and two product categories. A survey of 326 participants and three generational focus groups based in Germany provided results.

While ocean plastic was preferred, a strong market potential and high WTP for both recycled plastic types was identified. Possible barriers like negative quality perception or contamination risk proved to be mostly irrelevant. Fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) were preferred over luxury goods because of higher compensation of frequent consumption, while trust in brand proved to be more important than brand reputation for both product categories.

The study suggests that brand transparency and information on recycled plastic material determines product choice, while its requirements differ between generations. Relative WTP gradually increased with younger generations, concluding that especially demand for FMCG of recycled plastic offers promising present and future value.

Keywords: Sustainable Consumption, Consumer Behaviour, Recycled Plastic, Product Category Perception, Intergenerational Differences

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List of Abbreviations

FMCG	Fast-moving consumer good
N	Total sample size
NWTP	No Willingness to Pay
SD	Standard Deviation
TPB	Theory of Planned Behaviour
WTP	Willingness to Pay

1. Introduction

1.1 Problem Statement

The overuse of plastic in our everyday life is visibly exemplified by the accumulation of ocean plastic (Payne et al., 2019). It causes severe threats to global ecosystems and health (Heidbreder et al., 2019) and contributes to an increase in GHG emissions (Royer et al., 2018). The after-use externalities associated with plastic packaging account for an estimated \$40 billion, thus considerably exceeding profits made by the plastic packaging industry (MacArthur Foundation, 2016). Nevertheless, research has found that the plastic production is likely to double within the next 20 years. This would surpass by far current waste and recycling capacities (MacArthur Foundation, 2016)

The current short life expectancy of plastic packaging is a fatal design flaw. On average, it does not exceed one year (Payne et al., 2019), while today's plastic recycling rates are no higher than 9% globally (Geyer et al., 2017). Plastic is ubiquitous and crucial in our everyday life due to its flexibility, durability and low production costs (Heidbreder et al., 2019). It is therefore a challenge to find alternatives with the same qualities but a reduced environmental impact.

However, by reusing plastic waste material that would otherwise be incinerated or discarded on a landfill, the impact can be reduced severely (Huysveld et al., 2019). Recycled plastic is therefore not only less impactful than virgin plastic (Rajendran et al., 2012), but the recycling process itself can most of the times be less harmful than its alternatives incineration and landfill (Huysveld et al., 2019). While other alternatives to recycled plastic, like biodegradable plastic, do not aim at closing the loop, recycled plastic aims to support a circular material flow (Payne et al., 2019). This holds especially true for plastic found on beaches as part of marine litter. The plastic pieces collected through ocean clean-ups can create new value and could mitigate the current projections of plastic exceeding the weight of fish in the oceans by 2050 (Magnier et al., 2019, MacArthur Foundation, 2016). Yet the energy needed for heating and remolding plastic pieces can sometimes exceed the beneficial aspects of plastic recycling (Huysveld et al., 2019).

Clearly, plastic has the potential to be given more than just a linear value. It thus comes as no surprise that the European Commission has set an ambitious target to raise recycling rates of plastic packaging to 55% from currently 30% as part of the circular economy pact. It integrates waste recycling as a crucial component for Europe's future and predicts that the demand for recycled plastic packaging in Europe will increase four-fold by 2025 in comparison to 2015 (European Commission, 2018). This forecast shows that studies on the so called plastic crisis have been able to advocate the need for substantial change in the plastic industry within the political arena (Nielsen et al., 2020). However, only a remarkably small number of studies has so far given insights on how consumers think about recycled plastic in particular (Magnier et al., 2019). Also, the World Bank (2014) identified a strong demand to define the psychological drivers for a change in resource consumption (World Bank, 2014).

While consumer acceptance of recycled plastic has not yet been studied extensively, the topic of sustainability has experienced a steep rise in popularity as the effects of climate change become increasingly evident (Naderi & Van Steenburg, 2018). Green consumer products in particular have emerged during the last past years (Confente et al., 2019). Especially younger consumers seem to have repeatedly proven a higher positive attitude concerning sustainable behaviour and green consumption (Naderi & Van Steenburg, 2018). In line with that, a recent market study reveals that older consumers are more concerned about higher prices for sustainable products, especially regarding products of frequent purchase such as fast-moving-consumer-goods (FMCG) (Gilsenan, 2019). Consequently, this study will analyse to which degree age, more specifically the three generational cohorts of Generation X, Y and Z, has an impact on the purchase intention for recycled plastic products. The harmful environmental impact of FMCG in comparison to other products due to its faced paced consumption rate is another critical point this study will touch upon. In line with this, the study will explain how luxury goods made of recycled plastics are perceived and in which way the purchase intention for both product categories differs.

More specifically, the main focus of this study will relate to varying intentions towards two categories of recycled plastic. In analysing the willingness to pay (WTP) for products made from conventional plastic waste vs. plastic waste collected from beaches and oceans, the study examines the potential market values and future implications for circular plastic material use.

1.2 Research Questions

Derived from the issues described in the problem statement, the thesis will analyse the WTP and differences in product category (FMCG versus luxury goods), material perception (recycled versus ocean plastic) and generation (Generation X, Y and Z). As these components have so far not been adequately studied in literature, the thesis aims at closing a research gap in the field of the consumer acceptance of recycled plastic by applying an explanatory sequential mixed methods approach. The in-depth analysis will provide answers to following research questions:

- 1) *What is the willingness to pay for recycled plastic and ocean plastic products?*
- 2) *To what extent does the willingness to pay for recycled plastic products differentiate between*
 - a) *conventional recycled plastic and ocean plastic material?*
 - b) *luxury goods and fast-moving consumer goods?*
- 3) *In what way do Generation X, Y and Z differ in regard to*
 - a) *consumer preferences?*
 - b) *attitudes?*
 - c) *the willingness to pay?*

1.3 Thesis Structure

In order to answer the research questions, the thesis will first look into a theoretical assumption that explains how WTP statements are shaped. Afterwards, findings of other studies will be examined in a thorough literature review, aiming at further understanding variables for recycled plastic perceptions and relevant differences in the product categories FMCG and luxury goods. Furthermore, the intergenerational discourse will be analysed by characterizing the three studied generations. The conceptual framework will give an overview of the interplay of all relevant variables and its influence on the WTP. In the following the explanatory sequential mixed methods approach will be explained and results concerning WTP, material, product and generational factors will be examined. The discussion section will further reflect and debate on relevant insights and draw implications. Finally, recommendations for practice and further research as well as limitations will be mentioned. The conclusion will sum up the most important findings of the study.

2. Theoretical Framework

In order to understand how this research is constructed, it is important to understand the underlying theoretical assumption. As the theory of planned behaviour (TPB) by Ajzen (1991) is a concept commonly used to explain pro-environmental behaviour and WTP statements (Al Mamun et al., 2018), this study was also based on its basic assumptions. The TPB (Figure 1) assumes that the behaviour of an individual can be influenced and predicted by its behavioural intention. The intention is an indicator for the motivation and willingness of the individual towards the performance of a certain behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). It is influenced by three socio-cognitive factors: attitudes, social norm and perceived behavioural control (PBC). While attitudes are defined as the degree of negative or positive assessment concerning the specific

Figure 1: Theory of Planned Behaviour by Ajzen (1991)

behaviour in question, the social norm is understood to be ‘the perceived social pressure to perform or not to perform the behaviour’ (Ajzen, 1991). The PBC on the other hand can also directly influence the behaviour and indicates the degree to which an individual perceives its own actions to be easy or difficult to perform. For the purpose of this research the level of behavioural intention will be claimed as the intention to purchase a good at a certain price, as done in many studies (Al Mamun et al., 2018; Essoussi & Linton, 2010; Laroche et al., 2001). It is therefore assumed that the stated WTP will be influenced by the three aforementioned factors attitudes, social norm and PBC.

3. Literature Review

This section will outline current and relevant literature to help understand which variables could shape the WTP statements. It will summarize the most important findings of previous studies related to recycled plastic, product category and the intergenerational discourse. Moreover, this section will present the developed hypotheses used for answering the stated research questions.

3.1 Recycled and Ocean Plastic

Over the past years research on plastic waste has exponentially increased (Heidbreder et al., 2019; Nielsen et al., 2019). Studies in regard to health impacts, micro plastics, marine plastic pollution and respective policies have encountered a steep rise in numbers. Specifically, research on waste management and recycling of plastic has constantly developed, building a base for circularity in plastic waste treatment (Nielsen et al., 2019; Payne et al., 2019; MacArthur Foundation, 2016). Research on biophysical and technical innovation related to plastic waste (Kim et al., 2010; Ragaert et al., 2020), the environmental impact of recycled plastic (Huysveld et al., 2019; Rajendran et al., 2012) as well as consumer attitudes towards waste recycling (post-consumption) have been issued quite extensively already (McCarty & Shrum, 1994; Oztekin et al., 2017).

But while studies have found that consumers view product characteristics specifically targeting post-consumption (like the recyclability of a product) as environmentally relevant, purchasing alternative materials to virgin plastic like bioplastic were neglected as a possible sustainable choice in some studies (Heidbreder et al., 2019). Due to research gaps regarding consumer acceptance of circular waste schemes (Muranko et al., 2018) but also consumer knowledge gaps regarding the whole lifecycle of a product (Heidbreder et al., 2019), understanding the acceptance of recycled products, and specifically of recycled plastic, amongst consumers is still a challenge.

Although in some studies the positive environmental effects of recycled material were not considered amongst consumers, other studies could identify a clear consumer understanding of the environmental benefits for recycled or refurbished products (Magnier et al., 2019; Michaud & Llerena, 2010). The WTP for a recycled product was rated higher than for conventional products in several studies, thus accepting a price premium for the more sustainable alternative (Essoussi & Linton, 2010; Magnier et al., 2019).

Looking at current research on the WTP for recycled products it is evident that studies have focussed on a broad range of recycled materials rather than on the specific case of recycled plastic (Essoussi & Linton, 2010; Michaud & Llerena, 2010).

That is especially interesting because research has shown that consumers perceive plastic as environmentally harmful, but still continue to buy it due to its convenience and its advantageous character (Heidbreder et al., 2019). Hence although studies have shown that the recycling of plastic can offer great environmental benefits, especially in comparison to other waste treatment alternatives (Huysveld et al., 2019), consumer perceptions on it differ widely. A recent study focussed on the WTP for ocean plastic products fills this research gap to some extent, making clear that consumers are willing to pay more for an ocean plastic product than its conventional alternative (Magnier et al., 2019). However, the research misses out on the direct comparison to recycled plastic that does not stem from marine litter, thus not clarifying if consumers see a value in the recycled material because of it frees the oceans from litter, or because of a circular material flow.

While environmental benefits are considered by respondents in many studies concerning recycled materials, other factors can dominate the acceptance of recycled products. Perceived disgust towards recycled products (Meng & Leary, 2019), the fear of contamination (Baxter et al., 2017; Magnier et al., 2019; Meng & Leary, 2019) and the perceived risk of functional deficits (Essoussi & Linton, 2010; Achabou & Dekhili, 2013) can be obstacles for the consumer purchase decisions. These factors have not been researched extensively within the plastics sphere so far, which is why this thesis will have a closer look on the effect of perceived contamination and quality on the WTP for recycled and ocean plastic.

3.1.1 Contamination

Contamination in the plastic recycling process occurs due to difficulties in the after-use material separation. This could in return lead to impurities of the recycled plastic material (Baxter et al., 2017). However, in this thesis the term contamination rather relates to the consumer decision process, as it could be affected by the perceived contamination risks through the recycling of previously used or touched material (Meng & Leary, 2019).

The fear of contamination is a trait related to our ancestors. It is an important motive to avoid diseases caused by contact with an object that is potentially harmful to human health (Meng & Leary, 2019; Murray & Schaller, 2016; Rozin & Haidt, 2013). While sneezing or coughing are inherent physical reactions of the disease-avoiding system (Murray & Schaller, 2016), the emotion of disgust or discomfort are behavioural reactions of the very same system. Consumer decisions are therefore intuitively and evolutionarily directed towards the product with the least likeliness to be containing harmful disease (Meng & Leary, 2019).

Other scholars argue that the feeling of disgust did not only evolve biologically. It is argued that it is also a cultural reaction (Rozin & Haidt, 2013). Expressive behavioural and psychological reactions were therefore adopted and transmitted through social systems by our ancestors to avoid contamination and aspects linked to morality (Rozin & Haidt, 2013).

In a US study, Meng & Leary (2019) found that textiles made from recycled used plastic bottles could potentially risk a perception of contamination. A significant number of participants stated that they would not be willing to buy textiles from used plastic bottles due to perceived contamination risk.

H1a: Contamination negatively influences the WTP.

Additionally, the closeness to skin would make the use of recycled plastic more uncomfortable in textiles than in other products. In that sense, plastic bags made of the same material were accepted significantly higher, as they are worn not as close to the skin as T-shirts. Interestingly, the European study of Mangier et al. (2019) has shown low WTP statements for textiles as well. Other recycled plastic product categories like durables were perceived less contaminated.

H1b: A wearable good is perceived to be more susceptible of contamination than a cosmetic product.

3.1.2 Quality Perception

Many studies on consumer acceptance of recycled or remanufactured products have found that concern for functional or quality related risks could negatively influence the overall perception of the product (Achabou & Dekhili, 2013; Essoussi & Linton, 2010; Hamzaoui-Essoussi & Linton, 2014).

Essoussi & Linton (2010) could identify a significant correlation between perceived functional risk and the consumer purchase decisions. For some product types, lower WTP was linked to the fear of lower quality (Essoussi & Linton, 2010).

H2: The lower the quality perception, the lower the WTP.

As most studies focussed on technological products, recycled paper and textiles and not on recycled plastic per se, it will be of valuable insights to see if the perceived quality of recycled plastic is perceived as badly as in recycled materials of other studies.

3.2 Product Category

Several studies have discovered that WTP statements can vary depending on the product category. A study by Essoussi & Linton (2010) comparing recycled and refurbished products of different product categories identified a varying WTP depending on the nature of the product (Essoussi & Linton, 2010). Usual WTP statements for green consumption differ between a range of 5-15% additional to the original price of the conventional product (Walcher & Ihl, 2020).

The study of Magnier et al. (2019) researched how influential different product categories made of ocean plastic can be on the WTP, by focussing on textiles, durables and FMCG. The assumptions that frequency of the purchase as well as the perceived environmental impact influences the WTP statements was supported (Magnier et al., 2019).

H3a: Higher frequency of purchase positively influences WTP.

This finding matches another study that researched consumer perceptions on textiles made from recycled material. Achabou & Dekhili (2013) specifically looked at luxury textiles and measured which factors were important for the purchase decision of the consumer. Their findings identified negative effects connected to the recycled material, suggesting that luxury brands generally still depend on their reputation and the perceived quality of the product, which was rated low with the sustainable alternative (Achabou & Dekhili, 2013).

H3b: Brand reputation is more important for purchase of luxury goods than FMCG.

Additionally, the aforementioned frequency of purchase can be an influential variable with luxury purchases. Luxury goods are purchased less frequently and less plenty than FMCG and are therefore perceived to be not as endangering to the planet as other product categories (Achabou & Dekhili, 2013; Davies et al., 2012).

H3c: Relative WTP is higher for FMCG than for luxury goods.

3.3 Intergenerational Differences

The concept of a generation implies that people born within a certain time span have experienced the same historical and economic events. It is assumed that these events can influence attitudes and behaviours of people belonging to the same generational cohort (Gray et al., 2019; Koppetsch, 2016).

There is a wide discrepancy in literature on whether different generations show contrasting attitudes towards environmental behaviour (Diamantopoulos et al., 2003; Heidebreder et al., 2019; Wiernik et al., 2013). Some studies were able to identify clear differences in age and pro-environmental behaviour stating that either older (Otto & Kaiser, 2014) or younger (European Commission, 2017) consumers are more prone towards environmental beliefs and behaviour. Other scholars specifically researched generational cohorts and were not able to find correlations with environmental consumption (Gray et al., 2019).

These findings also match the current specific research on sustainable plastic. Magnier et al. (2019) identified four clusters of green consumers for the evaluation of ocean plastic products. A rather homogenous average age along the different clusters was indicating that no intergenerational difference in environmental attitudes could be identified (Magnier et al., 2019).

Nevertheless, constant segmentation and marketing reports identify notably the younger generations Y (1980-1994) and Z (1995-2012) to be of high environmental concern and to be

willing to pay more for sustainable products in comparison to Generation X (1965-1979) (Gilsenan, 2019; First Insight, 2020).

In order to understand what might be causing these differences in consumption and possibly also in environmental behaviour, the following section will explain typical characteristics of each generation. As the study was conducted in Germany, a special regard falls to historical events that presumably shaped the cohorts. The identification of generations into distinct time frames depends on the source (Töröcsik et al., 2014). As no source comprehensively defined the three generations altogether, this research identified the generational cohorts by combining the most suiting out of all defined time frames in literature.

3.3.1 Generation X

Generation X (1965-1979) has experienced economic uncertainties and grew up with more lower income single parent households due to rising divorce rates (Gray et al., 2019). Specifically in Germany high unemployment rates and the reunion of East and West Germany were very formative for the young adults of that time (Niproschke & Zylla, 2017).

The previous separation of private life and society through political power dysfunctions during World War II and the cold war strongly influenced the lifestyle of Generation X. They believe in the power of the collective and in the possibility of changing politics through revolutions from the bottom-up. These beliefs directly shaped personal traits like altruism and the trust in institutions (Koppetsch, 2016).

H4: Altruism is strongest for Generation X.

Generation X'ers are realistic and resourceful (Gray et al., 2019). Environmental issues were already important to most Generation Xers and were tackled with the power of the collective and the formation of a new environmental party in Germany (Koppetsch, 2016).

3.3.2 Generation Y

In contrast, Generation Y (1980-1994) is much more self-involved. Also referred to as Millennials, Generation Y was highly influenced by the rise of the internet and economic collapses, technological evolutions and globalization (Gray et al., 2019). In Germany, the introduction of a stricter unemployment policy called "Hartz Reformen" put more pressure on young adults to perform well in education and professional life. At the same time, the pressure to maintain or even exceed the living standards they knew from their parents was high. High consumption rates are a manifestation of that status elevation (Koppetsch, 2016) and are very characteristic for Generation Y (Naderi & Van Steenburg, 2018).

Other than Generation X, Millennials do not believe in the power of the collective anymore. They believe the past has shown that complex political structures cannot be influenced or revolutionized by collective citizen action. They rather believe in independent and individual success and show a strong distrust towards institutions (Koppetsch, 2016).

Neoliberalism, capitalism and flexibility in life are a given for Millennials. The responsibility for many sections in life therefore shifted from the collective to the individual level.

Generation Y is more egoistic, materialistic, brand sensitive and self-involved than other generations before (Gray et al., 2019; Koppetsch, 2016; Naderi & Van Steenburg, 2018). Hence also environmental issues are viewed as a personal choice and are important on an individual rather than on a political level (Koppetsch, 2016). Accordingly, studies on Millennials have shown that traits like materialism or egoism are not counteracting pro-environmental involvement or behaviour. This stands in contradiction to other studies that assume pro-environmental behaviour stems solemnly from altruistic traits (Naderi & Van Steenburg, 2018).

H5: Materialism does not affect the WTP.

3.3.3 Generation Z

The youngest generation of this analysis is called Generation Z (1995-2012). Z'ers were mainly influenced by digitalization, constant technological innovations, Social Media and constant availability of information. But also terrorism and heavy recessions are part of the upbringing of Generation Z (Niproschke & Zylla, 2017). Due to rising education levels, Generation Z is under high pressure to perform well and has less time for outdoor activities (Wood, 2013). It is the first global generation that is united through a globalized digitalization (OC&C, 2019; Wood, 2013). The introduction of the Euro in 2001 additionally marks a new era of union in Germany (Niproschke & Zylla, 2017).

Generation Z shares a homogenous affection for the same food and fashion and reject things that are too uniform or popular. The expression of individuality is very important, while high consumption rates are considered normal for Generation Z (OC&C, 2019; Niproschke & Zylla, 2017). For them the world seems chaotic, uncontrollable and unfair (“Die Gen Z konsumiert mit Bedacht”, 2019). Environmental uncertainties are a prime worry (Amnesty International, 2019; OC&C, 2019; Porter Novelli, 2019). In order to create an impact for a better world, issues like animal cruelty, sustainability and equality are very important in product choice (“Die Gen Z konsumiert mit Bedacht”, 2019).

H6a: Environmental concern is highest for Generation Z.

Purpose driven companies are much appreciated within Generation Z (OC&C, 2019; Porter Novelli, 2019) and a study has shown that the willingness to pay for such products is higher than for other generations (Gilsenan, 2019).

H6b: Relative WTP is highest for Generation Z in relation to their disposable income.

3.4 Summary

Figure 2 shows an overview of all relevant hypotheses grouped into the three important components of this study.

Figure 2: Overview of Hypotheses

The literature review indicated that various factors can influence the WTP statements of this research. While contamination and quality perception could be disadvantageous for the WTP, high frequency of purchase and brand reputation could have positive effects on the WTP of this study. Furthermore, the literature review shed light on the characteristics of the three generational cohorts, mainly looking at how altruism, materialism and environmental concern could shape the WTP statements.

4. Conceptual Framework

As the theoretical framework and the literature review already indicated, there are several variables that can influence pro-environmental behaviour. The conceptual framework (Figure 3) of this study therefore includes the influence of different variables regarding three overarching levels: material, generational and product factors. In this, the research combines

findings of other studies relating to the three levels in order to produce a holistic understanding on consumer acceptance of recycled plastic material.

Within the three levels, contrasting views of the respondents will become evident throughout the research and show how much weight they carry on the WTP statements. The conceptual framework furthermore centralizes the behavioural intention, in this case the WTP, as main outcome from the interaction with the relevant factors.

Figure 3: Conceptual Framework

5. Methods

The following section will describe the methodological approach of the study in order to comprehend how an in-depth analysis was attained.

This research made use of the explanatory sequential mixed methods approach (Ivankova et al., 2006) to precisely answer the stated research questions. The anticipated in-depth analysis of the topic through the mixed-methods approach allows for a triangulation of data and a more accurate understanding of the WTP statements and other variables (Ivankova et al., 2006).

In this, a survey was conducted in Phase 1 in order to statistically comprehend which variables are effectively influencing the behavioural intention towards recycled and ocean plastic.

In Phase 2, focus group discussions were conducted on the basis of the quantitative results.

With the help of descriptive statistics and inferential relationships identified in quantitative data, and causal relationships identified in the focus groups, the stated hypothesis will be able to be validated or rejected.

Figure 4: Visual Model for Mixed-Methods Sequential Explanatory Design Procedures

5.1 Quantitative Phase

5.1.1 Survey Design

Mostly close-ended questions were used in the survey. In most cases the items were measured using a five-point Likert scale. The duration of the survey was anticipated to be no longer than 6-9 minutes, in order to avoid large bounce rates. The survey tool Qualtrics was used for creation of the survey.

The survey was sectioned in attitudinal, material specific and product specific questions (see Appendix B). Variables like altruism, materialism, environmental concern and environmental knowledge were measured in the attitude section. A short explanation of the two different plastic types issued in this study was given and visually underlined before the material and product specific sections were tested.

Material specific questions measured the consumer perceptions about the two plastic types, while product specific variables tested the WTP and the perceived difference between two product types made of the two plastic materials.

In order to test both product categories, the example of sunglasses and shampoo bottle was picked for the luxury and the FMCG respectively. These were mainly selected because of their gender neutrality and overall common usage. A market analysis (see Appendix A) showed that both products already exist made of recycled plastic, indicating that the production of such products is not limited to the frame of this study only, but could certainly be used for managerial implications in reality.

The majority of variables were designed using existing scales (see Appendix B). In some cases the exact item was translated (Kilbourne & LaForge, 2010; Magnier et al., 2019; Schultz et al., 2005), in others adopted and slightly altered (Achabou & Dekhili, 2013; Ajzen, 1991; Meng & Leary, 2019; Smith, 2003; Taufique et al., 2016).

In order to measure the WTP of the participants, a picture and the common price for the very same product made of virgin plastic was listed (135€ for sunglasses; 3,69€ for a shampoo bottle). The participant was asked to indicate the WTP for four different products made of 100% recycled or ocean plastic on a slider, choosing any number between 135€ and 195€ (for Sunglasses) and 3,69€ and 7,69€ (for Shampoo Bottles). Participants could also indicate whether they would like to pay a higher price by clicking a button next to the slider (see Appendix C).

The pre-tests of the survey helped to refine the survey questions, especially in regard to the altruism scale and the length of the descriptive texts. Moreover, the pre-tests showed that not all participants were able to realistically answer the WTP for luxury sunglasses, which is why a follow-up question about the adequacy of price was introduced to understand possible results.

5.1.2 Data-Selection

The population of the survey was only limited by age, as this variable is directly linked to the intergenerational discourse of the study. Other demographic variables of the participant were not issue of exclusion. The population was limited to the aforementioned three Generations X, Y and Z due to time constraints of the research project. Generation Y was furthermore limited to participants of age 18 or older to avoid distortion effects. This is due to the fact that realistic WTP statements will be needed for accurate data-analysis. It is however assumed that minors do not reside in their own households, which makes a distortion of the WTP statements, especially for FMCG, more likely.

The total anticipated sample size for the survey was of at least 250 participants. Through random stratified sampling an equal response distribution amongst the three generations was ensured.

5.1.3 Data-Collection

For the data-collection of the survey, a snowball-system based on the researcher's personal network all around Germany was applied. The survey was also shared on social networks on Facebook consisting of young students (HWR Berlin), a survey platform (SurveyCircle.com) and a platform connecting local neighbourhoods (nebenan.de) in order to achieve as many homogenous touchpoints with the relevant target groups as possible. To further trigger interested people to participate and to counteract possible bounce rates, a prize incentive was advertised at the beginning of the survey.

5.1.4 Data-Analysis

The gathered survey data was analysed using the statistical analysis software SPSS. Mostly regression, correlation and Chi-Square Analysis were used to understand relationships between different variables. In this, the researcher aims to answer the developed hypotheses.

All participants born before 1965 and after 2002 were cleared out of the survey, as they do not belong to the previously mentioned generational cohorts. Moreover, the duration of filling in the survey was taken into account for the clearing process, as well as answer sets that showed participants had chosen the same value throughout the whole study.

Scales were combined to create single variables. For correct outcomes, the mean of these combined items was used for analysis. Additionally, the mean income was calculated by using the midpoint between each category. For the Multiple Regression Analysis dummy variables for each scale item have been created.

5.2 Qualitative Phase

In focus groups, participants discuss key questions of the research with other participants. They express their feelings, perceptions and thoughts towards critical statements and findings and thus give valuable insights in to what the core values, opinions and concerns of the participants towards the researched object are (Lynch et al., 2018).

5.2.1 Study Design

When designing the focus group sessions, it was taken into account that they should ideally last about 45 to 60 minutes. The whole focus group followed a semi-structured interview principle, giving the moderator a chance to ask further questions when a statement was especially striking or important. A short introductory text explaining the reasoning for this discussion, basic

discussion rules and a simple clarification of the difference between recycled and ocean plastic was prepared.

In the first part, the first questions were formulated in an open and broad manner for a rather simple entry to the discussion as suggested by Krueger et al. (2001). In this, the researcher focussed on understanding the general perception of recycled and ocean plastic products of the participants. The next set of questions aimed at integrating some of the quantitative results, such as the negative impact of contamination on ocean plastic sunglasses. The last question of the first part aimed at summing up the most important characteristics of recycled and ocean plastic products when considered for purchase.

For the second part of the survey, a short text on each generation was prepared. The question whether this would fit personally to the participants and whether they see differences amongst their generational peers was designed for a meaningful discussion within the focus group.

5.2.2 Participants

In order to understand possible causal relationships between results of the quantitative research that has been elaborated in the previous chapter, the focus groups were set up concentrating on the intergenerational aspect of the study. Hence, three focus groups according to the three generational cohorts were conducted. Due to the limitations of the Covid-19 pandemic, the number of participants was reduced and most of the discussions took place with the help of the web conferencing tool “Skype”.

A paper of Kite and Phongsavan (2017) suggests limiting the number of participants for a focus group held online, as the dynamics are different than in face-to-face meetings. Thus, in this particular case, the aim was to conduct focus groups with 3-4 people as suggested by research (Kite & Phongsavan, 2017). The group set up mainly concentrated on the variable age and fit to either one of the three generations. Furthermore, only German speaking participants were recruited.

Similar to the survey spreading process, the recruiting process for the focus groups made use of the snowball-system through the researcher’s personal network.

The participants were carefully recruited, incorporating individuals with different experiences, values and characteristics to generate a full and meaningful discussion (Krueger et al., 2001).

5.2.3 Implementation

The focus groups were held between June 1st and 3rd 2020. For the focus groups held online, a sharable Skype-Link was created enabling participants without Skype account to join the conversation. As one group did not have any concerns towards a face-to-face meeting with up to 5 participants (as current Covid-19 restrictions allowed), the focus group of Generation Z was held in person. The whole discussions were recorded. As various statements repeatedly

came up within the three focus group discussion, theoretical saturation was reached and no more discussions needed to be conducted (Krueger et al., 2001).

5.2.4 Data-Analysis

For analysis of the focus groups the note-based analysis was utilized (Krueger et al., 2001). The researcher took notes during the discussion and listened to the recordings one more time, noting the most important comments of the participants. Moreover, the analytical technique of the constant comparison analysis was applied for coding the data. First, smaller, similar units were combined and coded within the three focus groups. Then, the data was grouped in categories and larger themes were elaborated to stress the content of each category (Onwuegbuzie et al., 2009). This method is especially helpful when more than one focus group is interviewed, as it helps restructuring the arguments and understand saturation within and across the groups (Onwuegbuzie et al., 2009)

6. Results

This section examines the results of Phase 1 and 2. First, a general descriptive analysis will give insights about the participants' demographics. In the following, the results of the WTP analysis will be described. Further analysis on statements about recycled and ocean plastic and the product categories will be explored. Finally, the intergenerational discourse will show in what way the cohorts differ from each other. The result section aims at answering all mentioned hypotheses.

6.1 Participants

6.1.1 Participants of Quantitative Phase

The cleaning out process minimized the data set from 483 to 326 valid answers for analysis.

The sample of this survey consisted of 29,1% participants who identified as males, 70,2% participants who identified as females and 0,6% participants who identified as diverse (N=326). This relation shows an overrepresentation of females in the dataset, as the overall German population is made up of about 49,34% males and 50,65% females (Destatis, 2020).

The average age was calculated at 32,33 years (N=326; SD=10,10768). There is a relatively equal distribution amongst the sample of the study when looking at the generational cohorts of Generation X, Y and Z (see Table 1). The low standard deviation for Generation Z is explained by the smaller age margin of only 7 years (in comparison to 14 years for the other cohorts), as only participants aged 18 and older were accepted for the survey.

	Mean Birthyear	Mean Age	Standard Deviation	Share of total (in %)
Generation X	1971,99	48,01	4,72	23,3
Generation Y	1988,94	31,06	4,56	43,3
Generation Z	1996,94	23,06	1,73	33,4

The average net income of the participants was 1.715,34€ (N=326; SD=1436,03976).

The average income per generation differed largely (see Table 2). It is clear to see that Generation X had the largest mean income at their disposal. Generation Z indicated to only have a third of the income of Generation X (33,64%) monthly available.

	Mean Net Income (in €)	Standard Deviation
Generation X	2.635,53	1846,33
Generation Y	1.859,93	1114,18
Generation Z	886,70	995,53

6.1.2 Participants of Qualitative Phase

The focus group of Generation X consisted of one male participant (born 1970 (GXM1)) and two female participants (born 1971 (GXF1) and 1976 (GXF2)).

Generation Y consisted of two female participants (born 1990 (GYF1) and 1991 (GYF2)). One male participant (born 1985) could not join because of technical difficulties.

Generation Z was put together by one male participant (born 1998 (GZM1)) and two female participants (born 1997 (GZF1) and 1996 (GZF2)).

6.2 Willingness to Pay

6.2.1 Willingness to Pay Statements

Overall, the study suggests that the majority of participants was willing to pay more for recycled and ocean plastic products in comparison to the price for the very same product made of virgin plastic. Figure 3 shows that, on average, the WTP for ocean plastic was assessed higher than for recycled plastic. Hence, participants valued ocean plastic higher in both product categories concerning their WTP statements.

	Mean WTP (in €)	Standard Deviation	Increase relative to virgin plastic (in %)
Luxury Good			
Recycled Plastic	147,5997	12,0376	9,3
Ocean Plastic	152,2352	14,9309	12,77
FMCG			
Recycled Plastic	4,4306	,7327	20,05
Ocean Plastic	4,6159	,8264	25,20

In relation to the original price for the product made from virgin plastic, the participants were willing to pay up to 25% more for the sustainable alternatives, depending on plastic and product type. While the relative WTP for luxury goods is noted around the 10% mark, the relative WTP is more than double for the FMCG. It can clearly be noticed that luxury goods are valued high, but FMCG are valued even higher. This result validates H3c.

Although the WTP statements seem to show acceptance for a high price premium, the focus groups stated that the affordability of the products in comparison to the competition should be kept in mind. All three generations emphasized its importance. Although all participants stated to be willing to pay more for recycled plastic products, a comparison with the general product offer (either online or at the stores) would still be a crucial step in the purchase process.

“I can imagine that when Ray Ban puts ocean plastic sunglasses on the market, they will cost 20-30€ more. And I don't think that is justified. They should still be affordable.” (GXF2)

6.2.2 Not Willingness to Pay Statements

All answers that were placed at the lowest value of the scale, meaning at the equivalent of the virgin plastic product price (135€ for Sunglasses; 3,69€ for Shampoo), were separately analysed in the category “Not willing to pay” (NWTP). Figure 5 shows its frequency distribution for all four product categories. Almost a third of all participants were not willing to pay more for sunglasses made of recycled plastic. In contrast, only about half of those participants stated not wanting to pay more for the shampoo bottle made of ocean plastic. The decrease in NWTP statements is coherent with the increase in WTP statements from sunglasses made from recycled plastic to shampoo from ocean plastic. The Chi-Square Test showed a significant relationship between all four variables, indicating that each variable is related to one another. Thus, the participants who were not willing to pay for one product were generally also not willing to pay for the other ones.

Figure 5: NWTP compared with WTP (N=326)

6.3 Analysis of the Theory of Planned Behaviour

After looking at the WTP statements, the underlying theoretical basis of the TPB will be analysed in order to comprehend in which way the relevant variables have influenced the WTP of the participants.

Figure 6: Analysis of Theory of Planned Behaviour

(Spearman Correlation; *Significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed); ** Significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed); N=326)

TPB (Ajzen, 1991) suggests that attitude, social norm and perceived behavioural control are relevant factors that form the intention level (WTP statements) of an individual. Looking at Figure 6, it becomes clear that only few TPB variables show a significant correlation with the WTP statements. Attitude for both sunglasses and shampoo bottle made from ocean plastic shows a slightly positive significant correlation towards the WTP statements, and so does the social norm variable for the shampoo bottle made of ocean plastic.

However, most variables remain insignificant. That is why further variables according to the conceptual framework will be investigated during this analysis for a better comprehension of which factors influenced the WTP statements.

6.4 Recycled and Ocean Plastic

In order to answer hypothesis H1a, H1b and H2 it is crucial to have a look at the general perception of the two plastic types. The analysis will investigate the perceived differences between recycled plastic and ocean plastic material and thus aims at generating findings that are additional to current literature.

6.4.1 General perception of recycled and ocean plastic

Survey participants evaluated both materials, conventionally recycled plastic and ocean plastic, as advantageous and implied that there is a high relative benefit in comparison to products made from virgin plastic. Interestingly, the evaluated benefit does not differ between recycled and ocean plastic material (see Table 4).

The environmental impact of both plastic types was furthermore recognized and highly supported by all three generations in the focus groups. It was the most prevalent reason for the support of recycled and ocean plastic products.

The general attitude towards the two materials suggest that participants in the survey thought recycled plastic was slightly better than ocean plastic.

Table 4		
Differences in Perception of Plastic Types (<i>N</i> =326)		
	Mean	Standard Deviation
Relative Benefit		
Recycled Plastic	4,26	,914
Ocean Plastic	4,25	1,049
Attitude		
Recycled Plastic	4,02	,921
Ocean Plastic	3,91	1,202
Contamination		
Recycled Plastic	1,32	,709
Ocean Plastic	1,36	,771

Surprisingly, the variable for contamination was assessed low by the majority of participants for both plastic types (see Table 4 and Figures 8 and 9).

Figure 8: Perceived Contamination for Recycled Plastic

(N=326)

Figure 7: Perceived Contamination for Ocean Plastic

(N=326)

Also, contamination was low for all product types (see Figure 9). The fact that the material has been used before by unknown strangers and, in the case of ocean plastic, has been exposed to nature before the recycling process was introduced to the material, did not bother the participants to a high degree.

Figure 9: Differences in Contamination Perception between Products (N=326)

As Figure 10 suggests, quality perception was rated high in the survey. The four products were expected to perform well and to be of high quality with almost the same stated values amongst the four products. Although quality perception was high in the survey, the participants of the focus group suggest that haptics of the product are important when an actual product purchase is considered. The way the product feels in the hands of the participant would be a dominant argument for whether the product would be worth the price, especially because participants are not very familiar with the recycled plastic material yet.

Figure 10: Differences in Quality Perception between Products (N=326)

6.4.2 Influence of plastic type perception on WTP

In order to understand which variables related to recycled and ocean plastic were influencing the WTP statements, a Spearman Correlation Analysis as well as a Multiple Regression Analysis were conducted.

It can be noticed that the quality perception wasn't significant for any of the four products (see Table 5). Hence, the quality perception and fears of dysfunctions of recycled or ocean plastic did not influence the WTP statements, which therefore falsifies H2.

As three of four correlations show a weak negative significant correlation (see Table 5), it can be assumed that contamination has a slightly negative effect on the WTP statements. Some participants therefore indicated a lower WTP when they feared contamination or sensed disgust towards the analysed products. Hence, H1a can be validated.

	Quality		Contamination	
	Correlation Coefficient	Significance	Correlation Coefficient	Significance
Luxury Good				
Recycled Plastic	,061	,275	-,074	,181
Ocean Plastic	,018	,746	-,130*	,019
FMCG				
Recycled Plastic	,063	,257	-,123*	,026
Ocean Plastic	,064	,249	-,167**	,002

Furthermore, the contamination variable showed a significant coefficient towards one specific product in the Multiple Regression Analysis. Accordingly, people with high contamination fears tend towards a decrease of WTP of about 16,78€ (p=,037; N=326) for sunglasses made of ocean plastic in comparison to someone with low contamination fears.

The focus group analysis identified that the closeness to skin and eyes and uncertainty of origin could be a purchase barrier and therefore cause a decrease in WTP:

“[Sunglasses made of ocean plastic] are very tight around the eyes and you also wear it longer on the face.” (GXF1)

“There is often the discussion, like, but this is not new, it’s something old, and therefore, it is also worth less. And when you also think that it was fished out of the ocean and have no idea how long it has been swimming around there...” (GYF1)

This finding verifies H1b.

All focus group participants agreed that contamination and quality perception would not be of any concern for them personally, which was mainly due to the fact that they trusted the recycling process. Nevertheless, they identified that some consumers could have large knowledge gaps within the field of recycling and would not trust current recycling technologies. The fear of a largely reduced quality for products made of already used plastics could lead to a lower valuation (WTP) of the product. According to some participants, fear of contamination could also stem from knowledge gaps.

6.5 Product Category

As the WTP already suggested, FMCG were valued higher by the majority of participants. It will now be further analysed in what way participants differed between the two product categories and which product they favoured the most. This section aims to answer Hypotheses H3a and H3b.

6.5.1 Frequency of Purchase

When asked which products they were most likely to buy, the survey participants indicated a clear ranking. The two FMCG were voted first and second place, with shampoo made from ocean plastic as number one. Sunglasses made from recycled plastic were voted last. This ranking is congruent with the pattern that was explored with the WTP statements.

Figure 11: Ranking of Products (N=326)

In the focus groups it was argued that the ranking is comprehensive, as most people want to incorporate sustainability in their daily lives nowadays. It would be nice to support a product that “helps”. People would feel less guilty buying a product made from recycled material, especially in terms of the high consumption rates of FMCG.

“These are products the average citizen does not think about so much and so fast. You buy a shampoo bottle, a toothpaste, which are made of plastic. You buy it, use it for maybe a week, two weeks, a month and then you throw it away and buy it again.” (GXMI)

It was hence no surprise to the participants that the shampoo made of ocean plastic was ranked highest in the survey. It was argued that ocean plastic is perceived as a valuable and sustainable material that counteracts the littering of the oceans and deaths of sea life. The purchase of FMCG made of ocean plastic would increase the effect of doing “something good” because of frequent use. There would also be no long-term commitment hindering a purchase and product choice would be more flexible.

Interestingly, the multiple regression analysis indicated that frequency of purchase was also affecting WTP statements for luxury goods in more than one case. Purchasing a luxury good once a year, every 6 months and monthly indicated a higher WTP of 7,188€ (p=,021), 7,737€ (p=,021) and 14,623€ (p=,000) respectively for recycled plastic sunglasses in comparison to someone who never buys luxury goods. Equally, participants who buy luxury goods every 6 months and every month indicated a higher WTP for sunglasses of ocean plastic of 9,141€ (p=,029) and 13,572€ (p=,009) respectively in comparison to someone who never buys luxury goods.

This finding suggests that a higher frequency of purchase positively influences the WTP, thus validating H3a.

6.5.2 Brand Reputation and Trust in Brand

As Figure 12 suggests, the importance of brand reputation for the purchase shows a medium score for all four product categories. Brand reputation is slightly more important for luxury goods than for the FMCG.

Figure 12: Differences in Brand Reputation between Products (N=326)

However, further analysis shows that correlation between WTP and brand reputation is positive and significant for the two FMCG and sunglasses of ocean plastic, but not for sunglasses of recycled plastic. This result indicates that brand reputation is not only important for luxury goods, but also plays a role for FMCG. Thus, H3b is falsified.

	Brand Reputation		Trust	
	Correlation Coefficient	Significance	Correlation Coefficient	Significance
Luxury Good				
Recycled Plastic	,100	,073	,160**	,004
Ocean Plastic	,120*	,030	,107	,046
FMCG				
Recycled Plastic	,176**	,001	,000	,996
Ocean Plastic	,169**	,002	,021	,711

While some participants of the focus groups said that they would rather support a small business than a common brand, other participants argued that brand reputation is crucial for luxury goods:

“Ray Ban, of course has a reputation, they presuppose a certain quality. With a brand that I don't really know, I don't even know if it's actually high quality. Will those sunglasses really last for three years?” (GZF2)

For all three generations of the focus groups it was moreover important that the brand seems trustworthy and reliable. Popular and unknown brands alike would benefit from a purpose driven production and communication. According to the participants, especially for FMCG, the brand name and reputation is not as important as trust. This matches with mean scores for trust (see Figure 13). However, the Spearman Correlation Analysis (see Table 6) indicated that trust generally did influence the WTP.

Figure 13: Differences in Trust between Products (N=326)

According to Generation X, trust is lower for reputed brands with a large product variety. The sustainability aspect would be more trusted in brands that show a focus on sustainable production (and indicate such information on the packaging) rather than a large product offer.

Furthermore, notably the two younger generations mentioned one crucial factor for purchasing a product that outstrips the importance of brand reputation and trust.

The modern package design, especially in case of the FMCG, was mentioned more than once in both focus group discussions of Generation Y and Z. An appealing and modern look was considered as one of the most striking and competitive attributes of the shampoo bottles of both materials.

“That's what really matters to me, the design. If it looks really cool, I'll buy it, even if I don't really need it.” (GZF2)

6.6 Intergenerational Differences

Literature indicated that there are rather large differences between the three generational cohorts analysed in this study. The following analysis of quantitative and qualitative results will show whether intergenerational differences occur in this study as well. The section aims at answering hypotheses H4, H5, H6a and H6b.

6.6.1 Differences in WTP statements

The results of this survey show a striking WTP distribution for the generational cohorts (see Table 7). Despite the exceedingly lower income of Generation Z, the average WTP for all four products does not differentiate much and in one case (for shampoo made of ocean plastic) even exceeds the WTP of Generation X. The almost three times larger average income of Generation X therefore does not result in a larger WTP for any product category in comparison to Generation Z. Additionally, the ANOVA Test significantly proved that there are no differences in the WTP statements and generational cohorts. It can thus be concluded that H6b is verified. Interestingly, the WTP for FMCG of recycled plastic was rather low, while the ocean plastic counterpart was valued high within Generation Z. It can also be depicted that Generation X was most willing to pay for the luxury product.

	Generation X		Generation Y		Generation Z	
	Mean WTP (in €)	Standard Deviation	Mean WTP (in €)	Standard Deviation	Mean WTP (in €)	Standard Deviation
Luxury Good						
Recycled Plastic	148,86	13,58	147,26	11,71	147,17	11,32
Ocean Plastic	153,42	16,62	151,81	13,99	151,95	14,97
FMCG						
Recycled Plastic	4,46	,79	4,45	,73	4,38	,69
Ocean Plastic	4,58	,86	4,64	,81	4,61	,82

Although Generation Z showed a relatively high WTP despite a smaller average income, Generation Z indicated the same NWTP likeliness as the other generations. This was confirmed by the Chi-Square Test, which did not find any significant coefficients between the generational cohorts in terms of NWTP. Hence, young and old participants were equally likely not to pay more for the sampled products.

6.6.2 Characteristics

As the divided groups only consist of small datasets between 76 and 124 responses per generational cohort, Chi-Square Test and Spearman Correlation Analysis did not result in many interpretable outcomes. That is why mainly descriptive analysis will be used to gather valuable

information about the intergenerational difference of this study. Table 8 shows the general mean distributions amongst the most important variables for the intergenerational comparison.

Surprisingly, the environmental concern was assessed highest by Generation X and lowest by Generation Z. Therefore, H6a is falsified. This result is especially interesting when looking at the differing statements from Generation X and Z from the focus group discussions. While Generation X indicated to have developed into a more environmentally concerned state over the years, especially with becoming parents, Generation Z states that pro-environmental behaviour is a requirement of their generation. Non-conformity with sustainable practices would be mostly judged by peers of the same age.

	Generation X	Generation Y	Generation Z
Environmental Concern	4,23	4,07	3,88
Materialism	1,89	2,46	2,77
Altruism	3,74	3,71	3,65

Altruism showed no particularly large difference between the generations. There were furthermore no significant differences found conducting the Chi-Square Test, indicating that altruistic traits are on the same level for all three generations. Hence, H4 is falsified. Moreover, there is a clear difference in materialism, showing that both Generation Y and Z valued materialistic traits higher than Generation X.

	Generation X	Generation X	Generation X
Brand Reputation			
Luxury Good			
Recycled Plastic	2,55	2,65	3,00
Ocean Plastic	2,58	2,67	3,06
FMCG			
Recycled Plastic	2,39	2,47	2,72
Ocean Plastic	2,45	2,47	2,70
Trust			
Luxury Good			
Recycled Plastic	3,33	3,18	3,51
Ocean Plastic	3,33	3,23	3,60
FMCG			
Recycled Plastic	3,07	3,17	3,18
Ocean Plastic	3,07	3,11	3,21

The importance of brand reputation seems to be assessed slightly higher the younger the generation is (see Table 9). Trust seems to be a variable Generation Z assessed slightly higher in all cases. Generation Y shows a lower need of trust in the producer of sunglasses and a slightly higher need for trust in shampoo brands than Generation X.

6.6.3 Influence of materialism on WTP statements

Especially materialism seems to reveal interesting insights when looking at its effect on the WTP statements (see Table 10). Although it was rated on a medium level by the survey participants, materialism was only significant for one of the four WTP statements. As the other three WTP statements did not show significant correlations, it reveals that overall materialistic traits were not strongly influencing the WTP. As neither the Multiple Regression Analysis showed any relevant influences of materialism on the WTP for the four products, H5 can be validated.

Table 10
Relationship between Materialism and WTP
(Spearman Correlation; ** Significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed); N=326)

	Materialism	
	Correlation Coefficient	Significance
Luxury Good		
Recycled Plastic	-,057	,304
Ocean Plastic	,022	,691
FMCG		
Recycled Plastic	-,127**	,022
Ocean Plastic	-,063	,255

6.6.4 Differences in scepticism and need of information

One interesting result of the inferential analysis in regard to the intergenerational discourse relates to the origin of environmental beliefs. Notably, there was a strong relationship between the participants of Generation Y and the influence of the news and media outlets. This finding is also reflected by the focus group statements, that depict how Generation Y would deal with an unknown plastic type seen in a store or online shop. Unfamiliarity with the material and distrust towards the producer would generate suspiciousness that could hinder the purchase.

“It doesn't look familiar to me and that's why I would do some research, like what is it anyway?” (GYF2)

Not only Generation Y but also Generation X found it important to further gather unbiased information when considering purchasing a recycled or ocean plastic product. The use of the internet to understand the true purpose of the product and to inform oneself about the real environmental benefit was fundamental for both generations. In that, also critical viewpoints of

relevant news articles would be considered in the purchase decision process. Scepticism and the fear of greenwashing could be minimized.

“You can say, ok, I trust the industry, that it will be honest, but if you are a sceptic, then you should of course also find out about the companies that offer something like this, about what you can find on the internet, whether what is written [on the product] is really true. With many companies you also know that these are marketing strategies.” (GXF2)

Generation X showed to be the most sceptic and suspicious out of all the three generations. They emphasized the fact that greenwashing could reinforce profit-oriented firms in exploiting good-willing consumers that trust the brand without conducting unbiased research themselves.

Interestingly, Generation X also showed scepticism in regard to the process of waste disposal, especially criticizing German procedures.

“Then it is in the worst case a German plastic product, which has been shipped to China, which may have been processed into sunglasses in the Philippines, and you can buy it again in Germany. Then I would say, maybe it really does make more sense to fall back on a conventional product.” (GXM1)

Transparency of origin and production are therefore important factors for evaluating the product quality, possible contamination risk and also the environmental value.

When looking at Generation Z, the Chi-Square Test found that Social Media was the dominant origin of environmental beliefs. This finding was also supported by the focus group discussion of Generation Z. Moreover, Generation Z found transparent information stated by the brand itself to be enough to generate trust. They therefore indicated that they were less sceptic as the other two generations. Greenwashing as such was not a strong concern.

According to Generation Z, especially luxury brands could profit from a modern and transparent website that informs the consumer about the recycling processes and brand purpose in a professional manner.

“I wouldn't just trust a brand that says [the product is made of] ocean plastic and that's it. They'd have to show transparency, they'd have to have projects, show how people fish or something, and show the numbers - if that was the case, then definitely. If an advertisement is shown to me now, and I click on it because I find it interesting and don't find anything on the website, then that would be weird.” (GZM1)

Furthermore, Generation Z thought about a digital solution that brands should use for transparency purposes. A QR-Code printed at the back of the packaging could be especially interesting for FMCG for the additional transmission of valuable information about the purpose

of the brand. Transparency initiated by the brand itself would hence be enough for Generation Z to consider purchasing the product.

Despite the differences, all participants of the focus groups stated that additional information on the packaging of the product, in store and on the website of the product are crucial for recognizing the environmental problem and benefit deriving from recycled plastic. The higher the transparency, the higher would be the willingness to buy the product.

A key factor in the purchase decision process of all three generations would be the visualization of the material use. This was considered especially crucial for FMCG. Hence, the importance of an ecolabel was mentioned by all three cohorts as the most important characteristic.

“The labelling would be important for me to know exactly whether it was really recycled or not.” (GYF2)

Additionally, a focus group participant of Generation Y identified the percentage (and its display) of recycled plastic used for the product to be crucial, as this would have large consequences on the direct environmental impact of the product. Additionally, Generation X noted that a certification of some kind would be helpful for understanding the validity of the recycled material. Interestingly, one participant mistook the existing “recyclable plastic” with the “recycled plastic” ecolabel during the discussion.

6.6.5 Generation versus Age

In the intergenerational discourse it is crucial to look at the frequency distribution alongside age, in order to comprehend possible trends and verify the theory, that people belonging to one generation actually show the same tendencies.

The clearest example for such a tendency is observable looking at materialism (see Figure 14). When looking along the birthyears (X-axis), there is a clear increase in materialism (Y-axis) detectable, the younger the participants become.

Figure 14: Materialism alongside Age (N=326)

Another clear example for an intergenerational difference is noticeable for the frequency of purchase of FMCG and luxury goods. There is a decrease in FCMG and an increase in luxury goods the younger the participants are.

Figure 15: Frequency of Purchase alongside Age (N=326)

There are however larger fluctuations in regard to the attitude. It is evident that there are larger discrepancies the younger the participants become, with Generation Z having the largest fluctuations (see Figure 16).

Figure 16: Attitude alongside Age (N=326)

The same fluctuating pattern is depictable for other variables, like brand reputation or trust in brand (see Figures 17 and 18). It similarly appears that fluctuations get stronger the younger the participants are.

Figure 17: Brand Reputation alongside Age (N=326)

Figure 18: Trust alongside Age (N=326)

6.7 Summary of Result Section

The result section as shown various insights, verifying most hypotheses. While recycled and ocean plastic seem to have been evaluated equally good in most matters, the WTP for ocean plastic was still indicated higher.

Figure 19: Overview of validated and falsified Hypotheses

Furthermore, the purchase of FMCG was preferred over luxury goods. While brand reputation has shown not to be as important as trust, the three generational cohorts require different measures for fully trusting a brand or producer. However, the analysis has shown that the three generations indicated a rather similar average WTP for all four products, despite a decreasing average income the younger the generation was.

For a clear overview of all verified and falsified hypotheses, Figure 19 outlines the most important findings. All verified hypotheses are hence displayed in colour, while the falsified hypotheses are marked grey.

8. Discussion

The aforementioned results yielded valuable insights into what consumers think about and value in recycled and ocean plastic products. These results will now be further discussed, and relevant implications will be drawn.

8.1 Willingness to Pay

The aim of the WTP analysis was to find out how strongly consumers value products made from recycled and ocean plastic material.

The most striking result of this study was mentioned at the very beginning of the result section.

With a relative WTP ranging from 9 to 25%, all of the four products were evaluated considerably higher than the price for the virgin plastic alternative. This is especially striking when compared with results of other studies on green consumption, which only indicate an increase of about 5-15% (Walcher & Ihl, 2020). Especially recycled and ocean plastic in FMCG are thus accepted amongst consumers above the common average and have high market potential. Despite possible barriers, which will be further discussed in following sections, the WTP statements clearly showed that both plastic types are not only considered highly important from an environmental but also from a consumer perspective.

However, as a typical purchase decision consists of weighing out different options and their value for money, the recycled and ocean plastic products stand opposed to a high competition on the existing market. The comparison with conventional products offered on the market could therefore hinder the purchase at such a high price point, as indicated by the focus groups. The stated WTP of this survey might therefore not be a direct indicator for the ideal price accepted by the consumers on the real market, but it is certainly an indicator for the strong demand for more recycled and ocean plastic products voiced by the consumer.

Products made from recycled and ocean plastic material could therefore be very promising on a larger scale. In light of the current circularity strategy by the European Commission intending to increase current recycling rates in the EU (European Commission, 2018), this is an especially valuable insight. As this study found that the majority of consumers highly accepted both recycled plastic types, the increase of recycled plastic in all EU countries seems feasible and realizable, especially from a B2C perspective. It even seems as if consumers are asking for a higher proportion of recycled plastic as part of a more sustainable lifestyle.

8.2 Recycled and Ocean Plastic

The assessment of differences between the two plastic types and potential concerns about the perceived quality and contamination risk was a crucial component in the analysis of consumer acceptance of recycled and ocean plastic.

Both recycled plastic types were perceived well in the survey and the focus group discussion. Not many immediate differences occurred in the direct comparison regarding its perception, suggesting that, as long as an environmental benefit and a circular material flow can be detected, consumers would be highly likely to purchase a product made from both recycled plastic types alike.

Because of its additional positive impact on the environment, ocean plastic has however been evaluated higher in WTP in both product categories. More specifically it was rated about 3% higher in luxury and 5% higher in FMCG. The TPB analysis has shown that especially for ocean plastic, the positive attitude and social norm can positively influence the WTP.

While the additional environmental benefit in ocean plastic is evident to the consumers, both plastic types have overall shown high interest for purchase. This indicates that both materials would be equally accepted on the market. While ocean plastic might trigger even more people

towards a product because of its added value, it seems as if both recycled plastic types are welcome alternatives to virgin plastic products.

Although a possible lack in quality was issued in the focus groups, overall fears concerning the quality of recycled and ocean plastic were very low in both the quantitative and qualitative study. Contradictory to other studies for recycled material or refurbished products (Achabou & Dekhili, 2013; Essoussi & Linton, 2010; Hamzaoui-Essoussi & Linton, 2014), the WTP for recycled and ocean plastic did not suffer because of quality perceptions. Associations of lower quality might be of concern for single consumers, but the majority do not directly associate recycled or ocean plastic with low quality. Rather the contrary is the case, as the evaluation of the four products has shown that, on average, the participants assessed the quality of both plastic types medium high. This is a very promising result suggesting that previously assumed negative quality associations with recycled material might have shifted. Due to higher importance of sustainable lifestyles, as stated by the focus groups, negative quality associations and the feeling of buying something “used” could have overall decreased, while positive perceptions increased amongst the majority of consumers.

Moreover, the results concerning the factor contamination suggest that, generally speaking, consumers do not feel highly disgusted or uncomfortable because of recycled plastic material. Although recycled and ocean plastic originates from waste, the low contamination evaluation in both studies shows it is not associated as such by the consumer in most cases. This is in contradiction to existing studies on recycled plastic (Magnier et al., 2019; Meng & Leary, 2019). However, the results also suggest that it could negatively influence WTP in the rare case that contamination fears are high. Especially ocean plastic could suffer from high uncertainty concerning its origin and contact with possible contaminants. That is why especially sunglasses from ocean plastic are inclined to be valued lower by people with high contamination fears, as the closeness to skin and eyes, and a long wearing duration are major obstacles. In this, the results match with literature on textiles that found similar findings regarding contamination fears (Magnier et al., 2019; Meng & Leary, 2019).

As the results suggest, trust in the recycling process and technologies reinforce positive quality perception and low contamination fears of consumers. As few participants were hesitant in regard to both variables, a need for further reinforcement of communication on the safety of the recycling process itself was recognized. More knowledge about the recycling procedures might therefore eliminate still existing concerns.

8.3 Product Categories

The aim of the product category analysis was to find out differences between FMCG and luxury goods and related factors.

WTP and NWTP statements indicate that FMCG are considered of substantially higher value for the consumer in direct comparison with the luxury goods. This is mainly due to low commitment, affordability and high frequency of purchase. It seems as though consumers want to compensate their unsustainable, consumption- oriented behaviour and would be gladly

making small changes in their everyday life in purchasing less environmentally harmful products. It can thus be recognized that there is an especially high demand for integrating recycled plastic material into the products of daily life consumption. This indicates that the FMCG industry has a high bargaining power to actually shift consumer behaviour, as consumers want to participate in establishing a circular plastic use.

However, due to its fast-paced consumption rates, it is unclear whether the participants indicated such a high WTP for FMCG only because of the apparent short-term commitment. The consumers could test the product once, but may not consider consistently buying the sustainable plastic alternative. This would have large impacts on the development and distribution phase for products made from recycled plastic material. Although consumers in both studies seemed truly interested in the FMCG made of the two recycled plastic types, this obstacle could potentially hinder producers to fully commit to the use of recycled plastic material in their product range.

Moreover, brand reputation seems to be important for both product categories alike in this study. This is not in line with findings of Achabou & Dekhili (2013) that considered higher importance of brand reputation for luxury goods. Moreover, throughout the study it has been evident that people comprehend trust in brand to be of higher importance than brand reputation for both product categories. Consumers want to trust the brand that they are purchasing, especially when made of yet unfamiliar material. Factors like transparency and professional appearance are key for luxury goods but also FMCG and should not be neglected as otherwise the perceived value of the product could strongly decrease.

8.4 Intergenerational Differences

The intergenerational discourse analysed whether there exist differences between the three cohorts in regard to the stated WTP and attitudinal variables.

The WTP results are suggesting that there is on average a rather homogenous mean WTP alongside the three generations without large discrepancies between the cohorts. This indicates that there is a generally accepted price premium amongst all generational cohorts, which matches with results of Magnier et al. (2019). This insight could be especially crucial for products without specific target groups, as the product price could appeal to a large audience, if chosen appropriately.

Moreover, the results suggest that overall WTP was stated highest by Generation X, while Generation Z stated a much larger WTP in relation to their income. This finding supports results by the European Commission (2017) and Gilsenan (2019) for a higher WTP and eagerness for purchasing sustainable products. However, the results are also contradicting other findings in literature that state environmental behaviour is higher for older generations (Otto & Kaiser, 2014) or concern is equal between generations (Magnier et al., 2019).

This finding also stands in strong contrast to the environmental concern variable that showed highest values for Generation X and lowest values for Generation Z. As the focus group

discussion indicated, Generation X self-developed environmental concern consciously as part of getting older and becoming parents. Generation Z however perceives sustainability as a requirement of their generation. The own perception of what is high and low in terms of environmental concern could therefore be twisted, as the comparison with the “younger self” or peers of their own age could have influenced the answers of the participants. It is however clear to see that Generation Z values the studied products just as much as the other two generations, although their disposable income is significantly smaller. This goes to show that a long-term perspective on the integration of recycled plastic material and circular approaches for the future could be very effective, as especially younger consumers highly demand a shift in material use and would be willing to pay more for it.

The three generations also showed differences concerning expectations in transparency and information availability when it comes to the purchase of a product made of recycled plastic material.

The fact that Generation Z is demanding honest transparency by the producer suggests that they do not want to utilize the many channels of information at their disposal for their purchasing behaviour but rather buy items that do not need much reflection and research. They demand professional brands and products with evident purpose and are quick in the decision-making process. If the brand does not care about the consumer, in providing a modern design and a transparent offline and online presence, Generation Z simply will not buy it and move on to a competitor. The fact that Generation Z assessed importance of trust in brand highest amongst all cohorts further underlines this finding.

It was however evident that also the other two generations consider trust in brand to be a very important component, especially in times of greenwashing and marketing scams.

Generation Y showed that they largely distrust new products claiming to be more sustainable. A very important component of the purchase decision would be the individual research and reflection on the purpose of the product.

Generation X shared the same level of distrust and need for research, thus suggesting that the majority of consumers (especially the ones older than 25) will not be buying the studied products without further unbiased investigation. This characteristic shows that both generations feel responsible for their purchase on an individual level. If the product cannot convince through hard facts, neutral reporting and analytical impact assessments, both cohorts will not consider the purchase as they cannot ensure a positive impact through their own actions.

These findings illustrate the importance of establishing a trustworthy brand, that is truly sustainable in all its structures. It implies that providing only one product made from recycled or ocean plastic in an otherwise virgin plastic dominated product portfolio does not suffice, as the integrity and sincerity of the brand could easily be questioned.

The study also demonstrated the importance of the use of an ecolabel for all three generations. The use of recycled or ocean plastic has to be clearly recognizable, which matches with findings of other studies (Magnier et al., 2019; Magnier & Schoormans, 2015). It should also be distinguishable from current labels on the market, especially from the “recyclable” ecolabel, as the study showed that some consumers might confuse the two labels. For the consumer also

indication of the ratio of recycled or ocean plastic used can be important, as this changes the environmental impact of the product.

Contrary to expected results, all three generations showed a similar level of altruism in the survey. Accordingly, also younger individuals want to help others and are not as egoistic as sometimes portrayed in current literature (Naderi & Van Steenburg, 2018). However, the results also showed a clear trend to more materialism the younger the participants were, with highest rates in Generation Z. Interestingly, this study has proven that materialism doesn't influence the WTP negatively. Materialism and high consumption therefore do not hinder pro-environmental behaviour. This matches findings by Naderi & Van Steenburg (2018).

This trend however could be viewed critically as it could hinder real advances in the plastic crisis of today and the future. The fact that materialistic traits and high consumption rates are higher the younger the generation gets is worrisome in many ways. Perceived compensation through purchase of sustainable plastic could yield to overall higher consumption rates. As consumers perceive the products as environmentally neutral or even beneficial, they do not reflect on the many ways plastic could be reduced or avoided altogether. However, in order to achieve advances in the plastic crisis, consumers should understand that any sort of unnecessary plastic, even if recycled, is worse for the environment than no plastic at all. The fact that materialism does not affect green purchasing could therefore also lead to misunderstandings and simple compensation mechanisms that do not change the current system for the better.

Overall, it can be said that each generation shows its own characteristic tendencies, although some overlapping makes it harder to define clear lines between the different cohorts. Segmentation into generational cohorts is however still a valuable method in defining specific product and branding strategies and target groups. The differences in media and information use, trust in brand and visual appearance, greenwashing fears and WTP in relation to income could be insightful and helpful in selling and marketing the products made of recycled or ocean plastic materials efficiently.

8.5 Recommendations

In the following relevant theoretical and practical implications will be mentioned, that have been developed based on the findings of this research.

8.5.1 Suggestions for Further Research

This study gathered insights that could be the basis for further research on consumer perception of recycled and ocean plastic. Especially in terms of the WTP of FMCG, the findings suggest that further research on the ideal market price would be required, especially in comparison to other products made from virgin plastic.

Hence, choice experiments or even field experiments could yield valuable and realistic WTP results, as their methods imply a display of various products with different characteristics at the same time. In that, the participants would be confronted with a more realistic purchase

experience and would have to choose the most preferred option out of a set of choice cards or even a shelf in a supermarket.

Especially in times of lowered virgin plastic prices due to the ongoing oil price war, the price of recycled plastic products is a critical determinant for its competitiveness on the market.

The choice or field experiments could also question crucial factors like the overall design of the product or effectiveness of the ecolabel.

Furthermore, this study found some larger discrepancies considering Generation Z in terms of attitude, brand reputation and trust. It would therefore be interesting to further investigate the entirety of Generation Z in a couple of years, when more realistic purchasing statements can be expected.

8.5.2 Suggestions for Practice and Policy

As the study suggests, the industry has a high bargaining power to shift consumer behaviour. Moreover, there is a risk that consumers could justify overconsumption through compensation mechanisms and miss avoiding plastic use where it is crucial.

Besides that, recycled plastic still requires energy and other ecosystem services as initially stated and thus can sometimes even exceed the disadvantages of incineration or landfills.

That is why especially the FMCG industry should make good use of its bargaining power and social responsibilities by intendedly shifting the current wasteful system into a more circular one. As the common waste management principle suggests, there should be followed a hierarchic rule for the use of plastic. In a committed sustainable strategy of a company, the elimination and reduction of all used plastic overall would be the very first step to consider in the design of a new product. Only if plastic use cannot be reduced anymore, using recycled plastic material should be considered as a feasible option to replace virgin plastic. Stricter policies on product design and overall plastic use in the FMCG industry should be applied to support this shift. EU-wide subsidies could help trigger eco-innovations in packaging, while higher taxes on virgin plastic are needed to efficiently make plastic use less attractive.

As the market analysis (see Appendix A) suggests, not many FMCG brands have so far integrated a wholesome recycled plastic strategy in their product portfolio. The findings of this study could therefore be especially interesting for bigger brands in the FMCG sector. A strong emphasis on circular material use in the creation of new products is therefore not only crucial for environmental reasons but could also yield strong competitive advantages. It is evident that ambitious corporate sustainability targets need to go hand in hand with supporting circular governance regimes in order to hinder lax applications and exploitation of consumers.

The study also suggests that brand transparency and product information are very important for consumers of all generations. Showing transparency and displaying it in a professional and comprehensive manner should therefore also be a major principle in developing brands and products with a focus on recycled and ocean plastic material. Particularly easy access of information is necessary. That is why products should have integrated a recognizable ecolabel and a comprehensive description about all relevant product and plastic type details either on the

product packaging itself or at the point of sale. The introduction of EU standards for more transparency and an official ecolabel for recycled plastic and ocean plastic could help progress consumer acceptance even further. While ecolabels could be perceived as more trustworthy coming from an official authority rather than from a profit-oriented industry, a target for more information disclosure on recycled plastic products would oblige the industry to be more transparent with their consumers about relevant information.

Besides that, the study suggests that brands of both product categories need to develop an appropriate online presence, where transparent information about the source of plastic origin, recycling process details and production details are described. The brand could identify the exact location where the recycled plastic stems from or show a picture of the sea the ocean plastic originates from as part of eliminating uncertainties. Such information should be directly stated or at least linked on the specific product page of the website for easy access. The use of a QR Code on the packaging could hence be especially helpful for FMCG, as Generation Z suggested, as it could quickly guide the consumer to the right product page on the brand's website. Hence, especially products with a younger target group could profit by integrating new technological tools and relevant transparency information.

However, also voices of the media should not be neglected, as Generation X and Y have shown large scepticism and ambition for unbiased research. Public relations, especially for well researched and unbiased articles from renowned newspapers and magazines, are crucial for eliminating scepticism amongst the older consumers. Especially larger companies should avoid buying advertisements but rather develop a fruitful network of relevant media representatives, that are engaged in sustainability topics and have a critical view. Positive assessments will have a real and valid impression on the consumer and can strongly decrease fears of greenwashing.

Another implication drawn from the study is the fact that recycled or ocean plastic could still end up back in the oceans after use, just as every other product. The support of a closed loop cycle, by making consumers send back the used product to the company itself or a third party for further recycling could counteract this flaw in the system. This could be especially feasible for luxury brands as they produce in smaller margins and are usually in closer contact to their customers. The mechanism could further be enhanced by incentives for the consumer, making them actively participate in the recycling process of their used products.

8.6 Limitations

As the Covid-19 pandemic restricted all personal contacts, especially the organization and conduction of the focus group discussions was limited. Online focus groups did not yield the desired discussions between the participants as there was an extra conversation barrier. This was especially noticed in comparison to the focus groups conducted in person.

Because of time constraints, only 3 generations were analysed. It would have been interesting to further analyse older generations, because this would have surely generated even more distinguishable differences in the intergenerational discourse.

Survey findings, especially in regard to WTP and all personal traits like environmental concern or altruism, could be skewed because participants tend to answer questions in surveys the way they think is socially expected or accepted (Walcher & Ihl, 2020).

The development of scales with different items was used to counteract this phenomenon to some extent. It is however not completely assured that all participants actually value the environment and altruistic traits as much as they indicated in the survey. Moreover, especially in regard to the WTP statements, factors like warm glow of giving could have positively skewed the WTP. As the products contribute to the development of a circular plastic use, the satisfaction deriving from supporting such an innovation could have led to overestimations on the part of the participant (Abbott et al., 2013). These factors could lead to intention-behaviour gaps, as often stated in literature concerning WTP studies (Walcher & Ihl, 2020).

11. Conclusion

This study intended to determine the WTP for recycled and ocean plastic products within two product categories. A further focus was set on an intergenerational discourse aiming at understanding differences between three generational cohorts. Throughout the research, the explanatory sequential mixed methods approach was applied to specifically answer the research questions.

While the results have indicated a high WTP for all researched products with a relative ranging price premium of 9-25% superior of the virgin plastic product price, it was clear that the FMCG were preferred over luxury goods. Frequency of purchase and affordability as well as a low commitment were main reasons the relative WTP for FMCG was twice as high as for luxury goods.

Moreover, the two plastic types were evaluated throughout the study, indicating that ocean plastic is the preferred option because of its additional positive environmental value. The WTP for ocean plastic products was larger for both product categories. However, both plastic types were highly accepted and valued by the consumers. Contamination fears were low and quality perception was positive for both recycled plastic types, suggesting that consumers perceive the reuse of plastic material positively rather than negatively. Due to these results it can be concluded that there is a large discrepancy between consumer demand and actual offer of recycled or ocean plastic products on the current market.

Furthermore, the intergenerational discourse showed interesting differences in the analysis of Generation X, Y and Z. Although disposable income differed largely, the WTP of all three cohorts did not vary much from each other. It can thus be said that all generations would be willing to pay the same average price for all products, while the relative WTP was significantly highest for Generation Z in comparison to their disposable income. This indicates that there is not only present market potential, but also future value placed on products of recycled and ocean plastic.

Clear differences in attitudes further suggest that materialism is increasing while environmental concern is decreasing the younger the consumer is. Materialistic traits do not influence the WTP

negatively, which is mainly caused by the compensation effect green products like recycled or ocean plastic can have on the perception of consumers. Environmental concern might be higher for Generation X because of consciously developed concern, while Generation Z feels required to act sustainably all along.

Moreover, there were differences in consumer preferences between the three generations. While Generation Z expects a brand-sided introduction to the brand purpose and transparent information about the product (mostly on the internet), Generation Y and X feel the need to personally research on brand and product to eliminate greenwashing fears and distrust. A well rounded and transparent website and unbiased coverage in the media are therefore key indicators that can prove honesty and sincerity of the brand, which in return creates trust from consumer side. All three generations agreed that further product information at the point of sale as well as the visibility of ecolabels are important components that decide for or against the purchase of a product made from recycled or ocean plastic.

It can thus be concluded that recycled plastic and ocean plastic are both highly demanded by all three generations. Especially the FMCG industry could profit in developing further products made of the respective material, which would not only yield competitiveness on the market, but also contribute to the mitigation of the harmful environmental impact of its industry. A practical application of this thesis' findings could hence enrich not only environmental but also economic aspects.

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Appendix A: Market Analysis

a) Luxury Products

1	Brandname	Product	Man/Woman	Recycled	Marketprice'	Ocean	Marketprice	Link	Availability	Recycling Ratio
2	OTHERS									
3	Ocean Bottle	Reusable Bottle				x	€ 46,95	https://theoceanbottle.com/	EU	100% recycled Plastic
4	Gomi	Music Box		x			€ 299	https://www.gomi.design/ja	EU	
5	Vertex	Hangers				x	n/a	https://vertex.de/en/ocean-pl	DE	
6	American Express	Credit Card				x	n/a	https://www.americanexpress.com/us	US	
7	Bureo	Jenga Game				x	\$ 49,95	https://bureo.co/collections	EU, Norway, US, UK, NZ, South Korea, Switzerland, Japan, Canada	100% recycled fishing nets
8	Bureo	Frisbee				x	\$ 12	https://bureo.co/collections	EU, Norway, US, UK, NZ, South Korea, Switzerland, Japan, Canada	100% recycled fishing nets
9	Bureo	Watter Bottle Cage for Bikes				x	\$ 14,95	https://www.trekbikes.com/	EU, Norway, US, UK, NZ, South Korea, Switzerland, Japan, Canada	100% recycled fishing nets
10	Humanscale	Chair				x	\$ 1009	https://www.humanscale.co	US	1kg recycled fishing nets
11	From Waste to Wasted	Rum				x	n/a	https://fromwastetowasted.nl	EU	100% Ocean Plastic (Cap)
12	Gomi	Portable Charger		x			77 €	https://www.indigogo.com	Worldwide	100% recycled Plastic
13	Kevin.Murphy	Shampoo				x	€ 26	https://www.hair-shop.com/	Worldwide	100% Ocean Plastic
14										
15										
16	TEXTILES									
17	Adidas	Leggings	W	x		x	€ 84,95	https://www.adidas.com/us	Worldwide?	79 % recycler Polyester, 21 % Elastan
18	Adidas	Bikini	W	x		x	€ 37,95	https://www.adidas.de/beac	Worldwide?	78 % recycled Nylon, 22 % Elastan
19	Adidas	T-Shirt	M	x		x	€ 44,95	https://www.adidas.com/us	Worldwide?	100% recycled Polyester
20	Fair Harbor	Swim Shorts	M	x	\$ 68			https://www.fairharborcloth.com/	US	88% recycled Plastic (Bottles), 12 % Spandex
21	Fair Harbor	Pants	M	x	\$ 88			https://www.fairharborcloth.com/	US	67% Recycled Plastic (Bottles), 25 % Cotton, 8% spandex
22	Fair Harbor	Shirt	M	x	\$ 66			https://www.fairharborcloth.com/	US	75% Recycled Plastic (Bottles), 16 % Tencel, 9% Elastane
23	Girlfriend Collective	Leggings	W	x	\$ 68			https://www.girlfriend.com/	US, UK, AU	79% Recycled Plastic (Bottles), 21% spandex
24	Girlfriend Collective	Sports Bra	W	x	\$ 38			https://www.girlfriend.com/	US, UK, AU	79% Recycled Plastic (Bottles), 21% spandex
25	OLAS	Leggings	W	x	€ 53.97			https://www.olasoceantribe.com/	EU, UK, US, AU, CAN	78% recycled Plastic (Bottles), 22% Lycra
26	The Tropics	T-Shirt	M	x	\$ 30			https://thetropics.co/collect	n/a	50% recycled Plastic (Bottles), 50% recycled cottona
27	The Tropics	Shorts	M	x	\$ 95.00			https://thetropics.co/collect	n/a	92% Recycled Plastic (Bottles), 8% Spandex
28	Ganni	Bathingsuit	W	x	€ 139			https://www.net-a-porter.com	Worldwide	84 % recycled Polyamid, 16 % Elastan; Lining: 92 % recycled Plastic, 8 % Elastan
29	Ganni	Top	W	x				https://www.net-a-porter.com	Worldwide	100% recycled Polyester
										90 % ECONYL (recycled Nylon), 10 %

1	Brandname	Product	Man/Woman	Recycled	Marketprice' Ocean	Link	Availability	Recycling Ratio
30	Peony	Bathingsuit	W	x	€ 151	https://www.net-a-porter.cc	Worldwide	90 % ECONYL (recycled Nylon), 10 % Elastan
31	Staud	Skirt	W	x	€ 219	https://www.net-a-porter.cc	Worldwide	100 % recycled Nylon; Lining: 100 % Cotton
32	Fisch	Bikini	W	x	€ 84	https://www.net-a-porter.cc	Worldwide	65 % ECONYL (recycled Nylon and fishing nets), 35 % Elastan
33	Fisch	Bathingsuit	W	x	€ 237	https://fischswim.com/colle	Worldwide	Shell: 65% Econyl (fishing nets and nylon waste) 35% Elastane, Lining: 73% Nylon, 27% Elastane
34	Marcia	Dress	W	x	€ 355	https://marciawear.com/col	Worldwide	80% ECONYL (fishing nets and nylon waste); 20% Elastan
35	Marcia	Bathingsuit	W	x	€ 225	https://marciawear.com/col	Worldwide	80% ECONYL (fishing nets and nylon waste); 20% Elastan
36	Patagonia	Jacket	M	x	\$349	https://www.patagonia.com	Worldwide	n/a
37	Patagonia	Tshirt	M	x	\$ 45	https://www.patagonia.com	Worldwide	50-100% recycled material
38	Patagonia	Shorts	M	x	\$ 69	https://www.patagonia.com	Worldwide	n/a
39								
40								
41	ACCESSORIES							
42	Ecoalf	Sneaker		x	€ 79,90 - 89,90	https://ecoalf.com/de/sneak	EU	100% Ocean Plastic
43	Ecoalf	Travelbag		x	€ 149,90 - 199,90	https://ecoalf.com/de/suitc	EU	30% Ocean plastic, 70% recycled Polyester
44	Adidas	Sneaker		x	€ 179,95	https://www.adidas.de/ultr	Worldwide?	n/a
45	Triwa	Clock		x	n/a	https://www.triwa.com/see/page/sign-here-time-oceans/	Worldwide?	100% Ocean Plastic
46	Got Bag	Backpack		x	€ 89	https://got-bag.com/de/products/daypack		100% Ocean Plastic
47	Norton	Sunglasses		x	\$ 89- 129	https://www.nortonpoint.c	US	100% Ocean Plastic
48	Karūn	Sunglasses		x	€ 99-169	https://karunworld.com/prc	Canada	100% Ocean Plastic
49	Bureo	Sunglasses		x	\$ 219	https://bureo.co/collections/	Japan, Canada	100% recycled fishing nets
50	Jason Hyde	Earrings		x	\$ 28	https://jasonhyde.com/proc	US	n/a
51	Jason Hyde	Bracelet		x	\$ 38-58	https://jasonhyde.com/proc	US	n/a
52	Jason Hyde	Necklace		x	\$ 58	https://jasonhyde.com/proc	US	n/a
53	Costa	Sunglasses		x	\$ 219	https://www.rei.com/produ	Worldwide	100% recycled fishing nets
54	Anya Hindmarch	Bag	W	x	€ 554	https://www.net-a-porter.cc	Worldwide	n/a (recycled plastic bottles + virgin leather)
55	Cleanwaves	Sunglasses		x	265 €	https://www.cleanwaves.co	Worldwide	100% Ocean Plastic
56	Wayks	Backpack		x	199 €	https://wayks.com/collectio	Worldwide	91% recycled PET

b) FMCG

1	Brandname	Product	Recycled	Marketprice	Ocean	Marketprice	Link	Availability	Recycling Ratio
2	Cleaning Products								
3	Frosch	Kitchen, Bathroom, Glass Cleaner	x	1,99€ - 2,69€			https://frosch.de/Products/Clear	Germany	100%
4	Frosch	Dishwashing	x	1,69 €			https://frosch.de/Products/Alloe	Germany	100%
5	Frosch	Laundry Detergent	x	4,49 €			https://frosch.de/Products/Wash	Germany	100%
6	Fairy	Dishwashing Soap	x		x	1,39 €	https://shop.rewe.de/p/fairy-ultra	Germany	10% ocean, 90% recycled plastic
7	Ecover	Laundry Detergent	x	3,95 €			https://www.dm.de/ecover-woell	Germany	100%
8	Vernel	Fabric Softener	x	1,75 €		n/a	https://www.dm.de/vernel-weic	Germany	100%
9									
10									
11	Cosmetics								
12	Frosch	Handsoap	x	1,99 €			https://frosch.de/Products/Hand	Germany	100%
13	Frosch	Shower Gel	x	1,99 €			https://frosch.de/Products/Show	Germany	100%
14	Dr. Bronner's	Shower Gel	x	18,49\$			https://shop.drbronnner.com/pur	Canada, US	100%
15	Dr. Bronner's	Desinfectant	x	6,95 €			https://www.dm.de/dr-bronnners	Germany	100%
16	Schauma	Shampoo	x		x	1,35 €	https://www.dm.de/schwarzkopf	Germany	50% Ocean; 50% recycled
17	Nivea	Shower Gel	x	2,95 €			https://www.dm.de/nivea-dusch	Germany	100%
18	t by tetesept	Shower Gel	x	2,85 €			https://www.dm.de/t-by-tetesept	Germany	55%
19	Dove	Shower Gel	x	1,79 € x			https://www.dove.com/de/wash	Germany	100%
20	Dove	Bodymild	x	2,99 €			https://www.dove.com/de/skin-	Germany	100%
21	Dove	Shampoo	x	2,69 €			https://www.dove.com/de/hair-	Germany	100%
22	Dove	Conditioner	x	2,69 €			https://www.dove.com/de/hair-	Germany	100%
23	method	Handsoap	x		x	n/a	https://methodhome.com/beyor	US	100%
24	method	Handsoap	x	2,99\$			https://methodhome.com/prodi	US	100%
25									
26									
27	Utensils								
28	Preserve	Toothbrush	x				https://www.preserve.eco/collec	Worldwide	100%
29	Preserve	Toothbrush	x	3,49\$	x		https://www.preserve.eco/collec	Worldwide	25% Ocean Plastic, 75% recycled plastic
30	Grove Collaborative	Trash Bags	x	5,95\$			https://www.grove.co/catalog/p	Worldwide	100%
31									
32									
33	Food								
34	Share	Water Bottle	x			0,69 €	https://www.share.eu/recyclat/	Germany	100%
35	Hellmann's	Mayonnaise	x			n/a	https://www.unilever.com/news	US	100%
36	Coca Cola	Water/Lemonade Bottle	x			n/a	https://www.cocacolaep.com/m	Sweden	100%

Appendix B: Survey Structure

Variable	Survey Items	Reference
SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHICS		
<p>Text: This study deals with products made of recycled plastic as part of the research for the Master of Science in Environment and Resource Management at the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam.</p> <p>According to forecasts, by 2050 more plastic parts will be swimming in the sea than fish. At the same time, plastic production is expected to double by 2050. Recycling solutions that create new added value for discarded materials are slowly conquering the market. To understand the market potential for products made of recycled plastic, this research analyses the differences between generations and the product categories of luxury and consumer goods. The survey takes about 7-10 minutes. The data is kept anonymous and individual answers cannot be traced back to the respondents.</p> <p>Please complete the survey fully, as this is very important for the study. At the end of the survey, all participants have the chance to win a 25€ voucher for the online shop GOODBUY.EU! The winner will be notified within the next 4 weeks.</p> <p>Thank you very much for your participation!</p>		
Gender	Please indicate your gender : w/m/d	
Age	Please indicate your birthyear: 1965-2002	
ATTITUDE		
Environmental Concern	I am concerned about environmental problems.	Schultz et al., 2005
	I have avoided buying a product because it had potentially harmful effects to people/or the environment	Magnier et al. 2019
Environmental Knowledge	I know well what the term plastic soup means.	adapted from Taufique et al., 2016; Magnier et al., 2019
	I know the difference between recycled and ocean plastic.	self developed
	I know well about the consequences of plastic waste for the environment.	adapted from Taufique et al., 2016; Magnier et al., 2019
Materialism	I admire people who own expensive homes, cars, and clothes.	Kilbourne&LaForge, 2010
	I'd be happier if I could afford to buy more things.	Kilbourne&LaForge, 2010
Altruism	I would let a neighbor I did not know well borrow an item of value to me (like a dishes or tools).	adapted SRAS, Tom W Smith , 2003
	I would voluntarily look after a neighbor's I did not know well pet or children without being paid.	adapted SRAS, Tom W Smith , 2003
Frequency of purchase	How often do you purchase shampoo?	self developed with Achabou and Dekhili, 2013
	How often do you purchase luxury goods?	self developed with Achabou and Dekhili, 2013

Origins of normative beliefs	My environmental beliefs have been formed by: (multiple answers possible) my parents friends of same age older friends younger friends other family members school and other education the media social media current/past challenges in climate change environmental protests and activists historical events	
WTP		
Material specific		
Text: Recycled plastic is generally made by reheating and remoulding pieces from plastic waste. In many cases these plastic pieces used to be water bottles, plastic packaging and plastic bags. Nowadays, not only plastic waste can be recycled, also marine litter collected on beaches and in the oceans can be reused to create new products. Hence, old fishing nets, plastic bottles and other plastic pieces that used to pollute marine ecosystems can be recycled. This form of plastic is called ocean plastic. We will now look further into your attitudes concerning these two kinds of plastic.		
Relative Benefit (of recycled/ocean plastic impact)	I think products made of recycled plastic can help save the environment. I think products made of ocean plastic can help save the environment.	Magnier et al. 2019
Self-Expression/ Signalling Green Consumption	Buying products made of recycled plastics would communicate who I am and what is important to me to other people. Buying products made of ocean plastics would communicate who I am and what is important to me to other people.	Magnier et al. 2019
Attitude	General impression of recycled plastic is very good/ good/ bad / very bad General impression of ocean plastic is very good/ good/ bad / very bad	adapted from Magnier et al. 2019
Social Norm	Most people who are important to me would approve my purchase of recycled plastic. Most people who are important to me would approve my purchase of ocean plastic.	adapted from Azjen, 1991
Perceived behavioral Control	It seems like I have the all the means to buy recycled plastic products. It seems like I have the all the means to buy ocean plastic products.	adapted from Azjen, 1991
Contamination	I believe products made from recycled material are unsanitary because the material has been used before. I believe products made from ocean plastic material are unsanitary because the material has been used before.	self developed with Meng & Leary, 2019
Product specific		
Text: Today, various products made of recycled and ocean plastic already exist. However, most products do not contain 100% of the recycled material, but rather are a mixture of raw and recycled or ocean plastic. In the following we want to test your willingness to pay for products made 100% of recycled material. Note that the recyclability of the products is still given. Please indicate how much you would be willing to pay for these products:		
WTP Questions	Please indicate how much you would be willing to pay for:	
	Sunglasses RP (original price for virgin plastic alternative: 135€)	
	Sunglasses OP (original price for virgin plastic alternative: 135€)	
	Shampoo Bottle RP (original price for virgin plastic alternative: 3,69€)	
	Shampoo Bottle OP (original price for virgin plastic alternative: 3,69€)	
Quality Perception	In comparison the the conventional alternative (made out of virgin material), I expect ... Sunglasses RP to have poor/same/ better/excellent overall quality. Sunglasses RP Sunglasses OP Shampoo Bottle RP Shampoo Bottle OP	Magnier et al. 2019
Contamination	It would make me feel uncomfortable using : Sunglasses RP because the material has been used before. Sunglasses RP Sunglasses OP Shampoo Bottle RP Shampoo Bottle OP	self developed with Meng & Leary, 2019

Self-Expression/ Signalling Green Consumption	By buying ... Sunglasses RP I would make a better impression on other people	adopted from Magnier et al. 2019
	Sunglasses RP	
	Sunglasses OP	
	Shampoo Bottle RP	
	Shampoo Bottle OP	
Brand reputation	I only pay for ... if I trust the brand/producer.	self developed with Achabou and Dekhili, 2013
	Sunglasses RP	
	Sunglasses OP	
	Shampoo Bottle RP	
	Shampoo Bottle OP	
	If ... were produced by a well known brand (Ray Ban or Head&Shoulders), I would be willing to pay more for the product.	self developed with Achabou and Dekhili, 2013
	Sunglasses RP	
	Sunglasses OP	
Ranking	Please rank the products after most likeliness to buy	
	this ranking is due to the :	
	- frequency of purchase	
	- my general interest	
	- my actual need for this product	
	- my environmental concern	
	- other, please specify _____	
SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHICS		
Income	Please indicate your monthly netto income in EURO:	
	Under 100€	
	100-500€	
	500-1.000€	
	1.000-2.000€	
	2.000-4.000€	
	4.000-6.000€	
	6.000-10.000€	
Over 10.000€		
Residence	Please indicate your current county of residence:	
	Baden-Württemberg	
	Bayern	
	Berlin	
	Brandenburg	
	Bremen	
	Hamburg	
	Hessen	
	Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	
	Niedersachsen	
	Nordrhein-Westfalen	
	Rheinland-Pfalz	
	Saarland	
	Sachsen	
	Sachsen-Anhalt	
Schleswig-Holstein		
Thüringen		
Decline to answer		

Appendix C: Published Survey

Diese Studie thematisiert Produkte aus recyceltem Plastik im Rahmen der Forschungsarbeit für den Master of Science in Environment and Resource Management an der Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam.

Prognosen zufolge werden bis 2050 mehr Plastikteile im Meer schwimmen als Fische. Gleichzeitig soll sich die Plastikproduktion bis 2050 verdoppeln.

Recycling-Lösungen, die eine neue Wertschöpfung für weggeworfene Materialien schaffen, erobern langsam den Markt.

Um das Marktpotenzial für Produkte aus recyceltem Plastik zu verstehen, analysiert diese Forschung die Unterschiede zwischen Generationen und der Produktkategorien Luxus- und Gebrauchsgüter.

Die Umfrage dauert etwa 7-10 Minuten. Die Daten werden anonym behandelt, und individuelle Antworten können nicht zu den Befragten zurückverfolgt werden.

Bitte füllen Sie die Umfrage vollständig aus, da dies für die Studie sehr wichtig ist.

Am Ende der Umfrage haben alle Teilnehmer die Chance, einen 25€-Gutschein für den Online-Shop GOODBUY.EU zu gewinnen!

Der Gewinner wird innerhalb der nächsten 4 Wochen benachrichtigt.

Vielen Dank für Ihre Teilnahme!

Umfragenfortschritt
0% 100%

Zu welchem Geschlecht fühlen Sie sich zugehörig?

Bitte geben Sie Ihr Geburtsjahr an:

Umfragenfortschritt
0% 100%

Dieser Abschnitt enthält eine Reihe von Aussagen. Bitte geben Sie den Grad Ihrer Zustimmung an. Es gibt keine richtigen oder falschen Antworten.

Ich bin besorgt über Umweltprobleme.

trifft nicht zu trifft eher nicht zu teils, teils trifft eher zu trifft zu

Ich vermeide es, ein Produkt wegen seiner schädlichen Auswirkungen auf Menschen oder die Umwelt zu kaufen.

trifft nicht zu trifft eher nicht zu teils, teils trifft eher zu trifft zu

Ich weiß genau, was der Begriff "Plastiksuppe" bedeutet.

trifft nicht zu trifft eher nicht zu teils, teils trifft eher zu trifft zu

Ich bin mir über die Folgen von Plastikabfällen für die Umwelt im Klaren.

trifft nicht zu trifft eher nicht zu teils, teils trifft eher zu trifft zu

Ich kenne den Unterschied zwischen recyceltem Plastik und Ozeanplastik.

trifft nicht zu trifft eher nicht zu teils, teils trifft eher zu trifft zu

Ich bewundere Menschen, die teure Häuser, Autos und Kleidung besitzen.

trifft nicht zu trifft eher nicht zu teils, teils trifft eher zu trifft zu

Ich wäre glücklicher, wenn ich es mir leisten könnte, mehr Dinge zu kaufen.

trifft nicht zu trifft eher nicht zu teils, teils trifft eher zu trifft zu

Ich würde einem Nachbar, den ich nicht gut kenne, einen Gegenstand ausleihen, der einen gewissen Wert für mich hat (wie z.B. Geschirr oder Werkzeuge).

trifft nicht zu trifft eher nicht zu teils, teils trifft eher zu trifft zu

Ich würde freiwillig und ohne Entlohnung auf das Haustier oder Kind eines Nachbarn aufpassen, den ich nicht gut kenne.

trifft nicht zu trifft eher nicht zu teils, teils trifft eher zu trifft zu

Umfragenfortschritt
0% 100%

Wie oft kaufen Sie Waren des täglichen Bedarfs wie Shampoo, Zahnpasta oder Waschmittel?

- nie
- weniger als 1 mal im Jahr
- alle 6 Monate
- alle 2-3 Monate
- jeden Monat
- wöchentlich (oder mehr)

Wie oft kaufen Sie Luxusgüter wie Sonnenbrillen oder Kleidung von höherer Qualität?

- nie
- weniger als 1 mal im Jahr
- alle 6 Monate
- alle 2-3 Monate
- jeden Monat
- wöchentlich (oder mehr)

Meine Besorgnis über die Umwelt wurde geprägt von:

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Meinen Eltern | <input type="checkbox"/> Medien und Nachrichten |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gleichaltrigen Freunden | <input type="checkbox"/> Sozialen Medien |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Älteren Freunden | <input type="checkbox"/> Aktuellen Herausforderungen des Klimawandels |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Jüngeren Freunden | <input type="checkbox"/> Umweltprotesten und -aktivisten |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Anderen Familienmitgliedern | <input type="checkbox"/> Ich mache mir keine Sorgen um die Umwelt |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Historischen Ereignissen | <input type="checkbox"/> Andere, bitte angeben <input type="text"/> |

Der Kauf von Produkten aus ... würde anderen Menschen vermitteln, wer ich bin und was mir wichtig ist.

	trifft nicht zu	trifft eher nicht zu	teils, teils	trifft eher zu	trifft zu
... recyceltem Plastik	<input type="radio"/>				
... Ozeanplastik	<input type="radio"/>				

Mein allgemeiner Eindruck von ... ist:

	schlecht	eher schlecht	neutral	eher gut	gut
... recyceltem Plastik	<input type="radio"/>				
... Ozeanplastik	<input type="radio"/>				

Ich denke ich habe alle Möglichkeiten und Mittel, um Produkte aus ... zu kaufen.

	trifft nicht zu	trifft eher nicht zu	teils, teils	trifft eher zu	trifft zu
... recyceltem Plastik	<input type="radio"/>				
... Ozeanplastik	<input type="radio"/>				

Ich glaube, Produkte aus... sind unhygienisch, weil das Material schon einmal verwendet wurde.

	trifft nicht zu	trifft eher nicht zu	teils, teils	trifft eher zu	trifft zu
... recyceltem Plastik	<input type="radio"/>				
... Ozeanplastik	<input type="radio"/>				

Ich kaufe nur ... wenn ich der Marke oder dem Hersteller vertraue.

	trifft nicht zu	trifft eher nicht zu	teils, teils	trifft eher zu	trifft zu
... Sonnenbrille aus recyceltem Plastik	<input type="radio"/>				
...Sonnenbrille aus Ozeanplastik	<input type="radio"/>				
...Shampoo-Flasche aus recyceltem Plastik	<input type="radio"/>				
...Shampoo-Flasche aus Ozeanplastik	<input type="radio"/>				

Wenn ... von einer bekannten Marke (Ray Ban oder Head & Shoulders) produziert würde, wäre ich bereit, mehr für das Produkt zu bezahlen.

	trifft nicht zu	trifft eher nicht zu	teils, teils	trifft eher zu	trifft zu
... Sonnenbrille aus recyceltem Plastik	<input type="radio"/>				
...Sonnenbrille aus Ozeanplastik	<input type="radio"/>				
...Shampoo-Flasche aus recyceltem Plastik	<input type="radio"/>				
...Shampoo-Flasche aus Ozeanplastik	<input type="radio"/>				

Umfragenfortschritt

Bitte ordnen Sie die Produkte durch Ziehen des Items nach Ihrer höchsten Kaufwahrscheinlichkeit ein :

- Shampoo-Flasche aus Ozeanplastik 1
- Sonnenbrille aus recyceltem Plastik 2
- Sonnenbrille aus Ozeanplastik 3
- Shampoo-Flasche aus recyceltem Plastik 4

Diese Reihenfolge ist entstanden aufgrund:

- der potentiellen Häufigkeit meines Kaufs
- meines allgemeinen Interesses
- meines tatsächlichen Bedarfs an diesem Produkt
- der Höhe des Preises
- der positiven Umweltauswirkungen durch meinen Kauf
- Andere, bitte angeben

Bitte geben Sie Ihr monatliches Nettoeinkommen (nach Steuern) in EURO an:

Bitte geben Sie Ihren derzeitigen Wohnsitz an:

Das war's! Vielen Dank für Ihre Teilnahme!

Für SurveyCircle Nutzer (www.surveycircle.com): Der Survey Code ist: **RQFX-Y8RN-SGX4-T7PQ**

Wenn Sie die Chance auf den Gewinn eines 25€-Gutscheins für den Online-Shop GoodBuy.eu wahrnehmen möchten, geben Sie bitte Ihre E-Mail-Adresse an (diese Angabe wird separat zusammengefasst, so dass Ihre Antworten nicht zu Ihnen zurückverfolgt werden können):

Appendix D: Focus Group Questions

Part One

1. To what extent have you ever come into contact with recycled plastic or ocean plastic?
(Follow Up Question: Would this be an argument for buying a product?)
2. Imagine you see a shampoo bottle that was made of ocean plastic at a drugstore. What thoughts would come to your mind?
(Follow Up Question: What negative aspects would you notice?)
3. Shampoo made of ocean plastic generally scored best in the survey. Why do you think that is so?
4. Although women are not more environmentally conscious, or have stated that they buy everyday products more often than men, their willingness to pay for shampoo was generally higher (by about 15 cents). Why could this be?
5. Disgust or fear of contamination from the use of already used plastic is especially strong for sunglasses made of ocean plastic (16,78€). What could be the reason?
6. What would be important to you when buying recycled plastic or ocean plastic? Are there any differences between the types of plastics or products?
(Please refer to the examples of sunglasses and shampoo)

Part Two

1. To what extent do you feel you personally fit with the statement?
(Follow Up Question: Which statements were absolutely correct and which ones not at all?)
2. To what extent do you think the statements fit your entire generation based on your personal experiences?
3. Do you see a clear difference to older or younger people?

Description of Generation X:

Generation X (1965-1979) has experienced economic uncertainty and has grown up with lower-income households of single parents due to rising divorce rates. In Germany in particular, high unemployment rates and the reunification of East and West Germany were very characteristic of the young adults of this period. The previous political separation of private life and society during World War II and the Cold War strongly influenced the lifestyle of Generation X.

They went to demonstrations to draw attention to political grievances. Political successes made them believe in the power of the collective and in the possibility of changing politics through bourgeois revolution.

Environmental issues were and still are important for most of Generation Xers and were decisively addressed with the founding of a new environmental party in Germany (Die Grünen). Environmental awareness is therefore understood less as an individual concern and more as a matter for politics in general.

Description of Generation Y:

Generation Y (1980-1994), also known as the Millennials, has been strongly influenced by the rise of the Internet and economic collapses, technological developments and globalization. In Germany, the introduction of tighter unemployment policies, the Hartz Reforms, increased the pressure on young adults to perform well in education and employment.

High consumption rates are therefore very characteristic of Generation Y

They believe in independent and individual success and show distrust towards institutions.

Capitalism and flexibility in life matter for the Millennials. The perceived responsibility in many areas of life is therefore shifting from the collective to the individual level, making Generation Y more selfish, materialistic and brand-sensitive than other generations before.

Therefore, environmental issues are also seen as a personal decision and are important on an individual rather than a political level.

Description of Generation Z:

Generation Z is mainly influenced by digitalization, constant technological innovations, social media and the constant availability of information. But terrorism and severe recessions are also part of the education of Generation Z.

It is the first global generation united by globalised digitisation. Generation Z shares a homogeneous preference for the same food and fashion and rejects all things too uniform and popular. Above all, expression of individuality is very important to them.

For them, the world appears chaotic, uncontrollable and unfair. Environmental insecurity is a major concern. To have an impact for a better world, issues such as animal cruelty, sustainability and equality in product choice are very important. Purpose-built companies are highly valued within Generation Z.

Appendix E: SPSS Analysis

a) Participants:

		Gender			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
→ Valid	Male	95	29,1	29,1	29,1
	Female	229	70,2	70,2	99,4
	diverse	2	,6	,6	100,0
	Total	326	100,0	100,0	

```
DESCRIPTIVES VARIABLES=Birthyear_Corrected
/STATISTICS=MEAN SUM STDDEV MIN MAX.
```

Descriptives

[DataSet1] /Users/alysa/Desktop/VU/Thesis/Survey/SPSS/Step2_3.sav

Descriptive Statistics						
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Birthyear_Corrected	326	1965,00	2002,00	647978,00	1987,6626	10,10786
Valid N (listwise)	326					

* Custom Tables.

```
CTABLES
/VLABELS VARIABLES=Age_Categories Birthyear_Corrected DISPLAY=DEFAULT
/TABLE Age_Categories [C] BY Birthyear_Corrected [S] [MEAN, STDDEV, COLPCT.COUNT PCT40.1]
/CATEGORIES VARIABLES=Age_Categories ORDER=A KEY=VALUE EMPTY=EXCLUDE
/CRITERIA CILEVEL=95.
```

Custom Tables

		Birthyear_Corrected		
		Mean	Standard Deviation	Column N %
Age_Categories	1,00	1971,99	4,72	23,3%
	2,00	1988,94	4,56	43,3%
	3,00	1996,94	1,73	33,4%

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Income_Mean	326	50,00	12500,00	1715,3374	1436,03976
Valid N (listwise)	326				

		Income_Mean	
		Mean	Standard Deviation
Age_Categories	1,00	2635,53	1846,33
	2,00	1859,93	1114,18
	3,00	886,70	955,53

Age Cattergorie 1 = Generation X

Age Cattergorie 2 = Generation Y

Age Cattergorie 3 = Generation Z

b) WTP

		Statistics			
		WTP_Sunglasses_Recycled	WTP_Sunglasses_Ocean	WTP_Shampoo_Recycled	WTP_Shampoo_Ocean
N	Valid	326	326	326	326
	Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean		147,5997	152,2352	4,4306	4,6159
Median		147,6000	150,6300	4,3500	4,5000
Std. Deviation		12,03761	14,93085	,73274	,82464
Minimum		135,00	135,00	3,69	3,69
Maximum		195,00	195,00	7,69	7,69
Sum		48117,50	49628,69	1444,36	1504,78

	Age_Categories					
	1,00		2,00		3,00	
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation
WTP_Sunglasses_Recycled	148,86	13,58	147,26	11,71	147,17	11,34
WTP_Sunglasses_Ocean	153,42	16,62	151,81	13,99	151,95	14,97
WTP_Shampoo_Recycled	4,46	,79	4,45	,73	4,38	,69
WTP_Shampoo_Ocean	4,58	,86	4,64	,81	4,61	,82

c) NWTP

NoWTP_Sunglasses_R					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	,00	228	69,9	69,9	69,9
	1,00	98	30,1	30,1	100,0
Total		326	100,0	100,0	

NoWTP_Sunglasses_O					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	,00	246	75,5	75,5	75,5
	1,00	80	24,5	24,5	100,0
Total		326	100,0	100,0	

NoWTP_Shampoo_R					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	,00	254	77,9	77,9	77,9
	1,00	72	22,1	22,1	100,0
Total		326	100,0	100,0	

NoWTP_Shampoo_O					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	,00	266	81,6	81,6	81,6
	1,00	60	18,4	18,4	100,0
Total		326	100,0	100,0	

NoWTP_Sunglasses_O * NoWTP_Shampoo_R

Crosstab

Count

	NoWTP_Shampoo_R		Total
	,00	1,00	
NoWTP_Sunglasses_O	,00	217	246
	1,00	37	80
Total		254	326

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	61,770 ^a	1	,000		
Continuity Correction ^b	59,355	1	,000		
Likelihood Ratio	55,354	1	,000		
Fisher's Exact Test				,000	,000
Linear-by-Linear Association	61,580	1	,000		
N of Valid Cases	326				

a. 0 cells (0,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 17,67.
 b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

NoWTP_Sunglasses_R * NoWTP_Shampoo_R

Crosstab

Count

	NoWTP_Shampoo_R		Total
	,00	1,00	
NoWTP_Sunglasses_R	,00	206	228
	1,00	48	98
Total		254	326

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	68,173 ^a	1	,000		
Continuity Correction ^b	65,790	1	,000		
Likelihood Ratio	63,745	1	,000		
Fisher's Exact Test				,000	,000
Linear-by-Linear Association	67,964	1	,000		
N of Valid Cases	326				

a. 0 cells (0,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 21,64.
 b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

NoWTP_Sunglasses_O * NoWTP_Shampoo_O

Crosstab

Count

	NoWTP_Shampoo_O		Total
	,00	1,00	
NoWTP_Sunglasses_O	,00	228	246
	1,00	38	80
Total		266	326

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	82,065 ^a	1	,000		
Continuity Correction ^b	79,084	1	,000		
Likelihood Ratio	71,824	1	,000		
Fisher's Exact Test				,000	,000
Linear-by-Linear Association	81,813	1	,000		
N of Valid Cases	326				

a. 0 cells (0,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 14,72.
 b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

NoWTP_Sunglasses_R * NoWTP_Shampoo_O

Crosstab

Count

	NoWTP_Shampoo_O		Total
	,00	1,00	
NoWTP_Sunglasses_R	,00	211	228
	1,00	55	98
Total		266	326

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	60,542 ^a	1	,000		
Continuity Correction ^b	58,141	1	,000		
Likelihood Ratio	55,964	1	,000		
Fisher's Exact Test				,000	,000
Linear-by-Linear Association	60,357	1	,000		
N of Valid Cases	326				

a. 0 cells (0,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 18,04.
 b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

d) TPB

Correlations

		WTP_Sunglasses_Recycled	Social_Recycled	Attitude_Recycled	PBC_Recycled
Spearman's rho	WTP_Sunglasses_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	,030	,101
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,584	,068
		N	326	326	326
	Social_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,030	1,000	,349**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,584	.	,000
		N	326	326	326
	Attitude_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,101	,349**	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,068	,000	.
		N	326	326	326
	PBC_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,074	,174**	,235**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,184	,002	,000
		N	326	326	326

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

			WTP_Sunglasses_Ocean	Social_Ocean	Attitude_Ocean	PBC_Ocean
Spearman's rho	WTP_Sunglasses_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	,042	,146**	,070
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,452	,008	,207
		N	326	326	326	326
	Social_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,042	1,000	,336**	,188**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,452	.	,000	,001
		N	326	326	326	326
	Attitude_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,146**	,336**	1,000	,229**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,008	,000	.	,000
		N	326	326	326	326
	PBC_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,070	,188**	,229**	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,207	,001	,000	.
		N	326	326	326	326

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

			WTP_Shampoo_Recycled	Social_Recycled	Attitude_Recycled	PBC_Recycled
Spearman's rho	WTP_Shampoo_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	,114*	,045	,054
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,040	,416	,327
		N	326	326	326	326
	Social_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,114*	1,000	,349**	,174**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,040	.	,000	,002
		N	326	326	326	326
	Attitude_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,045	,349**	1,000	,235**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,416	,000	.	,000
		N	326	326	326	326
	PBC_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,054	,174**	,235**	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,327	,002	,000	.
		N	326	326	326	326

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

			WTP_Shampoo_Ocean	Social_Ocean	Attitude_Ocean	PBC_Ocean
Spearman's rho	WTP_Shampoo_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	,195**	,169**	,025
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,000	,002	,654
		N	326	326	326	326
	Social_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,195**	1,000	,336**	,188**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	.	,000	,001
		N	326	326	326	326
	Attitude_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,169**	,336**	1,000	,229**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,002	,000	.	,000
		N	326	326	326	326
	PBC_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,025	,188**	,229**	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,654	,001	,000	.
		N	326	326	326	326

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

e) Descriptives of attitudinal, material and product factors

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Concern_Combined	326	1,00	5,00	4,0429	,77836
Knowledge_Combined	326	1,33	5,00	3,7035	,86410
Materialism_Combined	326	1,00	5,00	2,4340	,99124
Altruism_Combined	326	1,00	5,00	3,6963	,87607
RelativeBenefit_Recycled	326	1	5	4,26	,914
RelativeBenefit_Ocean	326	1	5	4,25	1,049
Social_Recycled	326	1	5	3,23	1,183
Social_Ocean	326	1	5	3,36	1,234
Attitude_Recycled	326	1	5	4,02	,921
Attitude_Ocean	326	1	5	3,91	1,202
PBC_Recycled	326	1	5	3,80	1,043
PBC_Ocean	326	1	5	3,36	1,183
Contamination_Recycled	326	1	5	1,32	,709
Contamination_Ocean	326	1	5	1,36	,771
Valid N (listwise)	326				

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Deviation
Quality_Sunglasses_Recycled	326	1	5	3,87	,925
Quality_Sunglasses_Ocean	326	1	5	3,87	,911
Quality_Shampoo_Recycled	326	1	5	3,88	,911
Quality_Shampoo_Ocean	326	1	5	3,86	,912
Contamination_Sunglasses_Recycled	326	1	5	1,46	,916
Contamination_Sunglasses_Ocean	326	1	5	1,46	,893
Contamination_Shampoo_Recycled	326	1	5	1,42	,897
Contamination_Shampoo_Ocean	326	1	5	1,43	,918
Signalling_Sunglasses_Recycled	326	1	5	2,87	1,195
Signalling_Sunglasses_Ocean	326	1	5	2,96	1,257
Signalling_Shampoo_Recycled	326	1	5	2,68	1,206
Signalling_Shampoo_Ocean	326	1	5	2,72	1,242
Trust_Sunglasses_Recycled	326	1	5	3,33	1,245
Trust_Sunglasses_Ocean	326	1	5	3,37	1,253
Trust_Shampoo_Recycled	326	1	5	3,15	1,235
Trust_Shampoo_Ocean	326	1	5	3,13	1,227
BrandReputation_Sunglasses_Recycled	326	1	5	2,75	1,303
BrandReputation_Sunglasses_Ocean	326	1	5	2,78	1,336
BrandReputation_Shampoo_Recycled	326	1	5	2,53	1,274
BrandReputation_Shampoo_Ocean	326	1	5	2,54	1,293

f) Spearman Correlation of attitudinal and generational factors and WTP

Correlations

		WTP_Sunglasses_Recycled	RelativeBenefit_Recycled	Social_Recycled	Attitude_Recycled	PBC_Recycled	Contamination_Recycled	
Spearman's rho	WTP_Sunglasses_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	-,024	,030	,101	,074	-,060
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,661	,584	,068	,184	,281
	N		326	326	326	326	326	326
	RelativeBenefit_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	-,024	1,000	,374**	,501**	,154**	-,203**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,661	.	,000	,000	,005	,000
	N		326	326	326	326	326	326
	Social_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,030	,374**	1,000	,349**	,174**	-,054
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,584	,000	.	,000	,002	,334
	N		326	326	326	326	326	326
	Attitude_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,101	,501**	,349**	1,000	,235**	-,188**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,068	,000	,000	.	,000	,001
	N		326	326	326	326	326	326
	PBC_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,074	,154**	,174**	,235**	1,000	-,207**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,184	,005	,002	,000	.	,000
	N		326	326	326	326	326	326
	Contamination_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	-,060	-,203**	-,054	-,188**	-,207**	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,281	,000	,334	,001	,000	.
	N		326	326	326	326	326	326

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

			WTP_Sunglasses_Ocean	RelativeBenefit_Ocean	Social_Ocean	Attitude_Ocean	PBC_Ocean	Contamination_Ocean
Spearman's rho	WTP_Sunglasses_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	,050	,042	,146**	,070	-,118*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,371	,452	,008	,207	,034
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
RelativeBenefit_Ocean	RelativeBenefit_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,050	1,000	,370**	,535**	,160**	-,230**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,371	.	,000	,000	,004	,000
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
Social_Ocean	Social_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,042	,370**	1,000	,336**	,188**	-,050
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,452	,000	.	,000	,001	,364
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
Attitude_Ocean	Attitude_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,146**	,535**	,336**	1,000	,229**	-,199**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,008	,000	,000	.	,000	,000
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
PBC_Ocean	PBC_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,070	,160**	,188**	,229**	1,000	-,198**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,207	,004	,001	,000	.	,000
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
Contamination_Ocean	Contamination_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	-,118*	-,230**	-,050	-,199**	-,198**	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,034	,000	,364	,000	,000	.
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

			WTP_Shampoo_Recycled	RelativeBenefit_Recycled	Social_Recycled	Attitude_Recycled	PBC_Recycled	Contamination_Recycled
Spearman's rho	WTP_Shampoo_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	,107	,114*	,045	,054	-,072
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,053	,040	,416	,327	,193
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
RelativeBenefit_Recycled	RelativeBenefit_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,107	1,000	,374**	,501**	,154**	-,203**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,053	.	,000	,000	,005	,000
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
Social_Recycled	Social_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,114*	,374**	1,000	,349**	,174**	-,054
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,040	,000	.	,000	,002	,334
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
Attitude_Recycled	Attitude_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,045	,501**	,349**	1,000	,235**	-,188**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,416	,000	,000	.	,000	,001
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
PBC_Recycled	PBC_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,054	,154**	,174**	,235**	1,000	-,207**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,327	,005	,002	,000	.	,000
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
Contamination_Recycled	Contamination_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	-,072	-,203**	-,054	-,188**	-,207**	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,193	,000	,334	,001	,000	.
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

			WTP_Shampoo_Ocean	RelativeBenefit_Ocean	Social_Ocean	Attitude_Ocean	PBC_Ocean	Contamination_Ocean
Spearman's rho	WTP_Shampoo_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	,169**	,195**	,169**	,025	-,082
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,002	,000	,002	,654	,140
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
RelativeBenefit_Ocean	RelativeBenefit_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,169**	1,000	,370**	,535**	,160**	-,230**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,002	.	,000	,000	,004	,000
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
Social_Ocean	Social_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,195**	,370**	1,000	,336**	,188**	-,050
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	.	,000	,001	,364
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
Attitude_Ocean	Attitude_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,169**	,535**	,336**	1,000	,229**	-,199**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,002	,000	,000	.	,000	,000
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
PBC_Ocean	PBC_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,025	,160**	,188**	,229**	1,000	-,198**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,654	,004	,001	,000	.	,000
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
Contamination_Ocean	Contamination_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	-,082	-,230**	-,050	-,199**	-,198**	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,140	,000	,364	,000	,000	.
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

			WTP_Sunglasses_Recycled	Concern_Combined	Knowledge_Combined	Materialism_Combined	Altruism_Combined
Spearman's rho	WTP_Sunglasses_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	,127*	,061	-,057	,128*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,022	,270	,304	,020
		N	326	326	326	326	326
	Concern_Combined	Correlation Coefficient	,127*	1,000	,304**	-,365**	,141*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,022	.	,000	,000	,011
		N	326	326	326	326	326
	Knowledge_Combined	Correlation Coefficient	,061	,304**	1,000	-,174**	-,103
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,270	,000	.	,002	,064
		N	326	326	326	326	326
	Materialism_Combined	Correlation Coefficient	-,057	-,365**	-,174**	1,000	-,013
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,304	,000	,002	.	,809
		N	326	326	326	326	326
	Altruism_Combined	Correlation Coefficient	,128*	,141*	-,103	-,013	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,020	,011	,064	,809	.
		N	326	326	326	326	326

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

			WTP_Shampoo_Recycled	Concern_Combined	Knowledge_Combined	Materialism_Combined	Altruism_Combined
Spearman's rho	WTP_Shampoo_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	,179**	,000	-,127*	,158**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,001	,995	,022	,004
		N	326	326	326	326	326
	Concern_Combined	Correlation Coefficient	,179**	1,000	,304**	-,365**	,141*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,001	.	,000	,000	,011
		N	326	326	326	326	326
	Knowledge_Combined	Correlation Coefficient	,000	,304**	1,000	-,174**	-,103
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,995	,000	.	,002	,064
		N	326	326	326	326	326
	Materialism_Combined	Correlation Coefficient	-,127*	-,365**	-,174**	1,000	-,013
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,022	,000	,002	.	,809
		N	326	326	326	326	326
	Altruism_Combined	Correlation Coefficient	,158**	,141*	-,103	-,013	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,004	,011	,064	,809	.
		N	326	326	326	326	326

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

			WTP_Sunglasses_Ocean	Concern_Combined	Knowledge_Combined	Materialism_Combined	Altruism_Combined
Spearman's rho	WTP_Sunglasses_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	,142*	,075	,022	,130*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,010	,177	,691	,019
		N	326	326	326	326	326
	Concern_Combined	Correlation Coefficient	,142*	1,000	,304**	-,365**	,141*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,010	.	,000	,000	,011
		N	326	326	326	326	326
	Knowledge_Combined	Correlation Coefficient	,075	,304**	1,000	-,174**	-,103
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,177	,000	.	,002	,064
		N	326	326	326	326	326
	Materialism_Combined	Correlation Coefficient	,022	-,365**	-,174**	1,000	-,013
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,691	,000	,002	.	,809
		N	326	326	326	326	326
	Altruism_Combined	Correlation Coefficient	,130*	,141*	-,103	-,013	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,019	,011	,064	,809	.
		N	326	326	326	326	326

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

			WTP_Shampoo_Ocean	Concern_Combined	Knowledge_Combined	Materialism_Combined	Altruism_Combined
Spearman's rho	WTP_Shampoo_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	,169**	-,009	-,063	,157**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,002	,875	,255	,004
		N	326	326	326	326	326
	Concern_Combined	Correlation Coefficient	,169**	1,000	,304**	-,365**	,141*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,002	.	,000	,000	,011
		N	326	326	326	326	326
	Knowledge_Combined	Correlation Coefficient	-,009	,304**	1,000	-,174**	-,103
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,875	,000	.	,002	,064
		N	326	326	326	326	326
	Materialism_Combined	Correlation Coefficient	-,063	-,365**	-,174**	1,000	-,013
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,255	,000	,002	.	,809
		N	326	326	326	326	326
	Altruism_Combined	Correlation Coefficient	,157**	,141*	-,103	-,013	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,004	,011	,064	,809	.
		N	326	326	326	326	326

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

g) Spearman Correlation of material and product factors

Correlations

			WTP_Shampoo_Recycled	Quality_Shampoo_Recycled	Contamination_Shampoo_Recycled	Signalling_Shampoo_Recycled	Trust_Shampoo_Recycled	BrandReputation_Shampoo_Recycled	Ranking_Shampoo_Recycled
Spearman's rho	WTP_Shampoo_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	,063	-,123*	,144**	,021	,169**	,005
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,257	,026	,009	,711	,002	,925
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326	326
	Quality_Shampoo_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,063	1,000	-,119*	,116*	,060	,008	-,118*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,257	.	,031	,037	,283	,889	,033
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326	326
	Contamination_Shampoo_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	-,123*	-,119*	1,000	-,026	,086	,085	,015
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,026	,031	.	,645	,122	,126	,782
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326	326
	Signalling_Shampoo_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,144**	,116*	-,026	1,000	,132*	,304**	-,001
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,009	,037	,645	.	,017	,000	,990
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326	326
	Trust_Shampoo_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,021	,060	,086	,132*	1,000	,277**	-,138*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,711	,283	,122	,017	.	,000	,013
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326	326
	BrandReputation_Shampoo_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,169**	,008	,085	,304**	,277**	1,000	-,087
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,002	,889	,126	,000	,000	.	,116
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326	326
	Ranking_Shampoo_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,005	-,118*	,015	-,001	-,138*	-,087	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,925	,033	,782	,990	,013	,116	.
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326	326

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

			WTP_Shampoo_Ocean	Quality_Shampoo_Ocean	Contamination_Shampoo_Ocean	Signalling_Shampoo_Ocean	Trust_Shampoo_Ocean	BrandReputation_Shampoo_Ocean	Ranking_Shampoo_Ocean
Spearman's rho	WTP_Shampoo_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	,064	-,167**	,152**	,000	,176**	-,163**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,249	,002	,006	,996	,001	,003
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326	326
Quality_Shampoo_Ocean	Quality_Shampoo_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,064	1,000	-,108	,068	,007	,028	,045
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,249	.	,051	,223	,902	,619	,419
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326	326
Contamination_Shampoo_Ocean	Contamination_Shampoo_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	-,167**	-,108	1,000	-,014	,033	,088	,092
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,002	,051	.	,806	,548	,114	,097
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326	326
Signalling_Shampoo_Ocean	Signalling_Shampoo_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,152**	,068	-,014	1,000	,099	,294**	-,095
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,006	,223	,806	.	,076	,000	,088
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326	326
Trust_Shampoo_Ocean	Trust_Shampoo_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,000	,007	,033	,099	1,000	,262**	-,088
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,996	,902	,548	,076	.	,000	,114
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326	326
BrandReputation_Shampoo_Ocean	BrandReputation_Shampoo_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,176**	,028	,088	,294**	,262**	1,000	-,089
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,001	,619	,114	,000	,000	.	,107
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326	326
Ranking_Shampoo_Ocean	Ranking_Shampoo_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	-,163**	,045	,092	-,095	-,088	-,089	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,003	,419	,097	,088	,114	,107	.
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326	326

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

			WTP_Sunglasses_Ocean	Quality_Sunglasses_Ocean	Contamination_Sunglasses_Ocean	Signalling_Sunglasses_Ocean	Trust_Sunglasses_Ocean	BrandReputation_Sunglasses_Ocean
Spearman's rho	WTP_Sunglasses_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	,018	-,130*	,110*	,107	,120*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,746	,019	,046	,053	,030
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
Quality_Sunglasses_Ocean	Quality_Sunglasses_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,018	1,000	-,151**	,086	,079	,007
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,746	.	,006	,123	,157	,902
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
Contamination_Sunglasses_Ocean	Contamination_Sunglasses_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	-,130*	-,151**	1,000	-,075	-,011	,045
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,019	,006	.	,179	,841	,421
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
Signalling_Sunglasses_Ocean	Signalling_Sunglasses_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,110*	,086	-,075	1,000	,113*	,271**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,046	,123	,179	.	,042	,000
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
Trust_Sunglasses_Ocean	Trust_Sunglasses_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,107	,079	-,011	,113*	1,000	,317**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,053	,157	,841	,042	.	,000
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
BrandReputation_Sunglasses_Ocean	BrandReputation_Sunglasses_Ocean	Correlation Coefficient	,120*	,007	,045	,271**	,317**	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,030	,902	,421	,000	,000	.
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

			WTP_Sunglasses_Recycled	Quality_Sunglasses_Recycled	Contamination_Sunglasses_Recycled	Signalling_Sunglasses_Recycled	Trust_Sunglasses_Recycled	BrandReputation_Sunglasses_Recycled
Spearman's rho	WTP_Sunglasses_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	,061	-,074	,092	,160**	,100
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,275	,181	,098	,004	,073
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
Quality_Sunglasses_Recycled	Quality_Sunglasses_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,061	1,000	-,194**	,121*	,109*	,018
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,275	.	,000	,029	,048	,748
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
Contamination_Sunglasses_Recycled	Contamination_Sunglasses_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	-,074	-,194**	1,000	-,122*	,015	,054
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,181	,000	.	,027	,788	,333
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
Signalling_Sunglasses_Recycled	Signalling_Sunglasses_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,092	,121*	-,122*	1,000	,105	,255**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,098	,029	,027	.	,057	,000
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
Trust_Sunglasses_Recycled	Trust_Sunglasses_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,160**	,109*	,015	,105	1,000	,291**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,004	,048	,788	,057	.	,000
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326
BrandReputation_Sunglasses_Recycled	BrandReputation_Sunglasses_Recycled	Correlation Coefficient	,100	,018	,054	,255**	,291**	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,073	,748	,333	,000	,000	.
		N	326	326	326	326	326	326

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

h) Ranking

Ranking_Sunglasses_Recycled	326	1	4	3,15	,983
Ranking_Sunglasses_Ocean	326	1	4	2,86	,971
Ranking_Shampoo_Recycled	326	1	4	2,13	,993
Ranking_Shampoo_Ocean	326	1	4	1,86	1,009
Valid N (listwise)	326				

i) Descriptives of Intergenerational Differences

Custom Tables

		Concern_Combined Mean	Knowledge_Combined Mean	Materialism_Combined Mean	Altruism_Combined Mean
Age_Categories	1,00	4,23	3,91	1,89	3,74
	2,00	4,07	3,70	2,46	3,71
	3,00	3,88	3,56	2,77	3,65

		RelativeBenefit_Recycled Mean	RelativeBenefit_Ocean Mean	Social_Recycled Mean	Social_Ocean Mean	Attitude_Recycled Mean	Attitude_Ocean Mean	PBC_Recycled Mean	PBC_Ocean Mean	Contamination_Recycled Mean	Contamination_Ocean Mean
Age_Categories	1,00	4,16	4,22	3,17	3,25	3,87	3,88	3,84	3,39	1,25	1,25
	2,00	4,36	4,27	3,22	3,35	4,00	3,79	3,84	3,38	1,29	1,33
	3,00	4,21	4,26	3,28	3,45	4,17	4,10	3,72	3,30	1,41	1,47

		BrandReputation_Sunglasses_Recycled Mean	BrandReputation_Sunglasses_Ocean Mean	BrandReputation_Shampoo_Recycled Mean	BrandReputation_Shampoo_Ocean Mean
Age_Categories	1,00	2,55	2,58	2,39	2,45
	2,00	2,65	2,67	2,47	2,47
	3,00	3,00	3,06	2,72	2,70

		Trust_Sunglasses_Recycled Mean	Trust_Sunglasses_Ocean Mean	Trust_Shampoo_Recycled Mean	Trust_Shampoo_Ocean Mean
Age_Categories	1,00	3,33	3,33	3,07	3,07
	2,00	3,18	3,23	3,17	3,11
	3,00	3,51	3,60	3,18	3,21

j) Inferential Statistics of Intergenerational Differences

Altruism_Combined * Generation_X Crosstabulation

Count		Generation_X		Total
		,00	1,00	
Altruism_Combined	1,00	3	0	3
	1,50	2	2	4
	2,00	10	4	14
	2,50	15	5	20
	3,00	47	12	59
	3,50	45	15	60
	4,00	58	12	70
	4,50	46	12	58
	5,00	24	14	38
Total		250	76	326

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8,746 ^a	8	,364
Likelihood Ratio	8,892	8	,351
Linear-by-Linear Association	,212	1	,645
N of Valid Cases	326		

a. 6 cells (33,3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,70.

Altruism_Combined * Generation_Y Crosstabulation

Count		Generation_Y		Total
		,00	1,00	
Altruism_Combined	1,00	1	2	3
	1,50	3	1	4
	2,00	11	3	14
	2,50	13	7	20
	3,00	26	33	59
	3,50	36	24	60
	4,00	40	30	70
	4,50	34	24	58
	5,00	21	17	38
	Total		185	141

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8,729 ^a	8	,366
Likelihood Ratio	8,954	8	,346
Linear-by-Linear Association	,054	1	,816
N of Valid Cases	326		

a. 4 cells (22,2%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1,30.

Altruism_Combined * Generation_Z Crosstabulation

Count		Generation_Z		Total
		,00	1,00	
Altruism_Combined	1,00	2	1	3
	1,50	3	1	4
	2,00	7	7	14
	2,50	12	8	20
	3,00	45	14	59
	3,50	39	21	60
	4,00	42	28	70
	4,50	36	22	58
	5,00	31	7	38
	Total		217	109

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	10,536 ^a	8	,229
Likelihood Ratio	10,951	8	,204
Linear-by-Linear Association	,431	1	,512
N of Valid Cases	326		

a. 5 cells (27,8%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1,00.

Generation_Z * NoWTP_Shampoo_R

Crosstab

Count		NoWTP_Shampoo_R		Total
		,00	1,00	
Generation_Z	,00	168	49	217
	1,00	86	23	109
Total		254	72	326

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	,092 ^a	1	,761		
Continuity Correction ^b	,026	1	,871		
Likelihood Ratio	,093	1	,761		
Fisher's Exact Test				,888	,439
Linear-by-Linear Association	,092	1	,762		
N of Valid Cases	326				

a. 0 cells (0,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 24,07.
b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Generation_Z * NoWTP_Shampoo_O

Crosstab

Count		NoWTP_Shampoo_O		Total
		,00	1,00	
Generation_Z	,00	174	43	217
	1,00	92	17	109
Total		266	60	326

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	,860 ^a	1	,354		
Continuity Correction ^b	,602	1	,438		
Likelihood Ratio	,879	1	,348		
Fisher's Exact Test				,449	,220
Linear-by-Linear Association	,857	1	,354		
N of Valid Cases	326				

a. 0 cells (0,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 20,06.
b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Generation_Z * NoWTP_Sunglasses_R

Crosstab

Count

	NoWTP_Sunglasses_R			Total
	,00	1,00		
Generation_Z	,00	148	69	217
	1,00	80	29	109
Total		228	98	326

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	,930 ^a	1	,335		
Continuity Correction ^b	,700	1	,403		
Likelihood Ratio	,942	1	,332		
Fisher's Exact Test				,371	,202
Linear-by-Linear Association	,927	1	,336		
N of Valid Cases	326				

- a. 0 cells (0,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 32,77.
 b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Generation_Z * NoWTP_Sunglasses_O

Crosstab

Count

	NoWTP_Sunglasses_O			Total
	,00	1,00		
Generation_Z	,00	163	54	217
	1,00	83	26	109
Total		246	80	326

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	,042 ^a	1	,838		
Continuity Correction ^b	,005	1	,946		
Likelihood Ratio	,042	1	,838		
Fisher's Exact Test				,892	,476
Linear-by-Linear Association	,042	1	,838		
N of Valid Cases	326				

- a. 0 cells (0,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 26,75.
 b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Origin_News * Generation_Y Crosstabulation

Count

		Generation_Y		Total
		,00	1,00	
Origin_News	0	43	20	63
	Medien und Nachrichten	142	121	263
Total		185	141	326

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4,212 ^a	1	,040		
Continuity Correction ^b	3,651	1	,056		
Likelihood Ratio	4,316	1	,038		
Fisher's Exact Test				,047	,027
Linear-by-Linear Association	4,199	1	,040		
N of Valid Cases	326				

- a. 0 cells (0,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 27,25.
 b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Origin_SoMe * Generation_Z Crosstabulation

Count

		Generation_Z		Total
		,00	1,00	
Origin_SoMe	0	123	38	161
	Sozialen Medien	94	71	165
Total		217	109	326

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)	Point Probability
Pearson Chi-Square	13,819 ^a	1	,000	,000	,000	
Continuity Correction ^b	12,960	1	,000			
Likelihood Ratio	13,987	1	,000	,000	,000	
Fisher's Exact Test				,000	,000	
Linear-by-Linear Association	13,777 ^c	1	,000	,000	,000	,000
N of Valid Cases	326					

- a. 0 cells (0,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 53,83.
 b. Computed only for a 2x2 table
 c. The standardized statistic is 3,712.

k) ANOVA-Test

Descriptives

WTP_Sunglasses_Recycled

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
1,00	76	148,8566	13,57991	1,55772	145,7534	151,9597	135,00	195,00
2,00	141	147,2567	11,71338	,98644	145,3065	149,2070	135,00	195,00
3,00	109	147,1670	11,34366	1,08653	145,0133	149,3207	135,00	180,00
Total	326	147,5997	12,03761	,66670	146,2881	148,9113	135,00	195,00

Test of Homogeneity of Variances

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
WTP_Sunglasses_Recycled	Based on Mean	1,654	2	323	,193
	Based on Median	1,639	2	323	,196
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	1,639	2	320,134	,196
	Based on trimmed mean	1,777	2	323	,171

ANOVA

WTP_Sunglasses_Recycled

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	157,056	2	78,528	,540	,583
Within Groups	46936,794	323	145,315		
Total	47093,850	325			

Descriptives

WTP_Sunglasses_Ocean

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
1,00	76	153,4217	16,61843	1,90626	149,6242	157,2192	135,00	195,00
2,00	141	151,8126	13,99178	1,17832	149,4829	154,1422	135,00	195,00
3,00	109	151,9548	14,96628	1,43351	149,1133	154,7962	135,00	195,00
Total	326	152,2352	14,93085	,82694	150,6084	153,8621	135,00	195,00

Test of Homogeneity of Variances

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
WTP_Sunglasses_Ocean	Based on Mean	2,754	2	323	,065
	Based on Median	2,821	2	323	,061
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	2,821	2	321,975	,061
	Based on trimmed mean	2,898	2	323	,057

ANOVA

WTP_Sunglasses_Ocean

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	140,752	2	70,376	,314	,730
Within Groups	72311,575	323	223,875		
Total	72452,327	325			

Descriptives

WTP_Shampoo_Recycled

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
1,00	76	4,4587	,79413	,09109	4,2772	4,6402	3,69	7,69
2,00	141	4,4545	,73111	,06157	4,3327	4,5762	3,69	7,69
3,00	109	4,3800	,69353	,06643	4,2483	4,5117	3,69	7,69
Total	326	4,4306	,73274	,04058	4,3507	4,5104	3,69	7,69

Test of Homogeneity of Variances

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
WTP_Shampoo_Recycled	Based on Mean	,381	2	323	,683
	Based on Median	,366	2	323	,694
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	,366	2	316,737	,694
	Based on trimmed mean	,390	2	323	,677

ANOVA

WTP_Shampoo_Recycled

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	,419	2	,210	,389	,678
Within Groups	174,078	323	,539		
Total	174,497	325			

Descriptives

WTP_Shampoo_Ocean

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
1,00	76	4,5762	,86094	,09876	4,3795	4,7729	3,69	7,52
2,00	141	4,6436	,81303	,06847	4,5082	4,7790	3,69	7,69
3,00	109	4,6077	,82012	,07855	4,4520	4,7634	3,69	7,69
Total	326	4,6159	,82464	,04567	4,5260	4,7057	3,69	7,69

Test of Homogeneity of Variances

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
WTP_Shampoo_Ocean	Based on Mean	,065	2	323	,937
	Based on Median	,228	2	323	,796
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	,228	2	316,441	,796
	Based on trimmed mean	,176	2	323	,839

ANOVA

WTP_Shampoo_Ocean

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	,236	2	,118	,172	,842
Within Groups	220,773	323	,684		
Total	221,009	325			

1) Multiple Regression Analysis

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	149,400	11,907		12,547	,000
	Purchase_FMCG_1year	-5,698	14,076	-,045	-,405	,686
	Purchase_FMCG_6months	-10,418	12,398	-,235	-,840	,401
	Purchase_Luxury_6months	5,970	3,128	,238	1,909	,057
	Purchase_Luxury_1year	7,188	3,111	,286	2,311	,021
	Purchase_Luxury_3months	7,737	3,339	,248	2,317	,021
	Purchase_FMCG_3months	-8,812	12,280	-,365	-,718	,474
	Purchase_Luxury_1month	14,623	4,130	,278	3,540	,000
	Purchase_FMCG_1month	-8,246	12,297	-,335	-,671	,503
	Purchase_FMCG_weekly	-8,910	12,618	-,169	-,706	,481

a. Dependent Variable: WTP_Sunglasses_Recycled

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	151,010	14,816		10,192	,000
	Purchase_FMCG_1year	-1,489	17,514	-,010	-,085	,932
	Purchase_FMCG_6months	-9,559	15,427	-,174	-,620	,536
	Purchase_Luxury_6months	5,800	3,892	,186	1,490	,137
	Purchase_Luxury_1year	7,456	3,870	,239	1,927	,055
	Purchase_Luxury_3months	9,141	4,155	,236	2,200	,029
	Purchase_FMCG_3months	-6,230	15,280	-,208	-,408	,684
	Purchase_Luxury_1month	13,572	5,139	,208	2,641	,009
	Purchase_FMCG_1month	-5,145	15,301	-,169	-,336	,737
	Purchase_FMCG_weekly	-3,802	15,700	-,058	-,242	,809

a. Dependent Variable: WTP_Sunglasses_Ocean

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	152,511	5,736		26,590	,000
	RelativeBenefit_O_SLow	-9,009	6,857	-,114	-1,314	,190
	Social_O_SLow	-,802	3,586	-,019	-,224	,823
	Attitude_O_SLow	-1,884	5,103	-,027	-,369	,712
	PBC_O_SLow	-3,086	4,327	-,082	-,713	,476
	Contamination_O_SLow	-3,413	2,383	-,083	-1,433	,153
	RelativeBenefit_O_Medium	1,134	6,175	,023	,184	,854
	Social_O_Medium	2,324	3,416	,065	,680	,497
	Attitude_O_Medium	1,318	4,039	,035	,326	,744
	PBC_O_Medium	-,873	4,275	-,027	-,204	,838
	Contamination_O_Medium	-4,637	3,881	-,069	-1,195	,233
	RelativeBenefit_O_SHigh	-,066	5,864	-,002	-,011	,991
	Social_O_SHigh	,859	3,307	,027	,260	,795
	Attitude_O_SHigh	4,090	4,007	,121	1,021	,308
	PBC_O_SHigh	-,445	4,299	-,013	-,103	,918
	Contamination_O_SHigh	8,561	7,675	,063	1,115	,266
	RelativeBenefit_O_High	-2,765	5,756	-,092	-,480	,631
	Social_O_High	-,310	3,623	-,008	-,086	,932
	Attitude_O_High	5,363	3,956	,178	1,356	,176
	PBC_O_High	-3,566	4,351	-,098	-,820	,413
	Contamination_O_High	-16,778	8,007	-,138	-2,095	,037

a. Dependent Variable: WTP_Sunglasses_Ocean

Appendix F: Codebook of Focus Group Discussions

Product Characteristics	Barriers	The Consumer
<p>Look & Feel</p> <p>Gen X: importance of haptic; positive impression; eco-labels; certificates</p> <p>Gen Y: eco-label draw attention; positive impression; importance of haptics; modern design; less value because used material; eco-labels; design of product packaging; emphasis on good quality</p> <p>Gen Z: eco-labels draw attention; importance of eco-label for recognition; positive impression; eco-labels; design of product packaging</p>	<p>Hesitation</p> <p>Gen X: scepticism; fear of greenwashing; Pragmatism; closeness to skin; duration of usage (long for SG) uncertainty of origin (ocean and contaminants); ingredients and actual need</p> <p>Gen Y: scepticism; closeness to skin</p> <p>Gen Z: pragmatism; closeness to face</p>	<p>Transparency and Knowledge</p> <p>Gen X: fear of greenwashing; need for unbiased information to eliminate scepticism; transparency to eliminate scepticism; clarity about origin</p> <p>Gen Y: need for unbiased information to eliminate scepticism; clarity about origin</p> <p>Gen Z: need for transparency; need for information (brand sided); QR Code for extra Information; transparency creates trust; clarity about origin</p>
<p>Impact</p> <p>Gen X: importance of sustainable living; impact through purchase frequency; FMCG are waste in itself; usefulness of project; regionality and packaging free; no environmental behavioural change due to covid-19</p> <p>Gen Y: less guilt; support of new innovation; no environmental behavioural change due to covid-19 (no visibility)</p> <p>Gen Z: clarity of environmental benefit (Ocean P); impact through purchase;</p>	<p>Recycling Process</p> <p>Gen X: trust in recycling process; BUT DOESN'T TRUST HOW THINGS END UP IN OCEAN</p> <p>Gen Y: fear of reduced quality; clarity about recycling rate</p> <p>Gen Z: knowledge gap about recycling process; clarity about recycling process</p>	<p>Usage</p> <p>Gen X: Clothing sector; Familiarity through work; easy product-testing (FMCG); daily product (FMCG)</p> <p>Gen Y: supermarket; no commitment (FMCG); luxury goods not present;</p> <p>Gen Z: supermarket; habituation to high prices (F); product testing (M)</p>

<p>contribution to social infrastructures; against animal cruelty; social issues of high importance; no environmental behavioural change due to covid-19 (no visibility)</p>		
<p>Brand specific</p> <p>Gen X: Brand-loyalty (M); affordable prices; trust in brand; brand focus and reputation;</p> <p>Gen Y: affordability; trust in brand; brand reputation</p> <p>Gen Z: affordable prices; short decision process FMCG; trust in brand for small brands; attention for product details (F); brand purpose ; website design;</p>		<p>Influence on purchase decision</p> <p>Gen X: media presence(F); willingness for Product-Testing; social media as advocator of useful projects; self-taught pro-environmentalism; income dependant</p> <p>Gen Y: regular engagement (F)</p> <p>Gen Z: travels; media; Social media scams;</p>
		<p>Generation specific</p> <p>Gen X: no homogeneity; (self-taught pro-environmentalism; focus on regionality and individual impact)</p> <p>Gen Y: feel fully represented; high consumption; altruism exists; Individuality in regard to consumption; flexibility in occupation and lifestyles; homogeneity amongst generation</p> <p>Gen Z: sustainability is required; individuality; social media as information tool; Homogeneity divided in two groups; (social issues of high importance)</p>

Appendix G: Additional Analysis

a) Residency of participants

As the study was distributed over different channels, people from all over Germany participated. About half of the participants were residents of the German capital Berlin. The rest of the participants were distributed among the country with larger numbers in North Rhine-Westphalia, Bavaria, Baden-Württemberg, Brandenburg and Hessen (See Figure 1), therefore most notably parts of western Germany were represented in this study.

Figure 1: Residency distribution; N=326

b) Adequacy of prices

The price for the luxury good in the survey was indicated quite high in order to match current market prices. Therefore, an additional option of indicating a preferred and more realistic price was given.

The analysis of this variable has shown that a large number of the participants (43,9%) thought the presented price for the luxury good was too high and suggested new WTP statements for both plastic types. However, some participants indicated in the given text field that those prices are meant for sunglasses of low to medium quality. The average price for sunglasses made of recycled plastic was hence indicated lower, at an average of 60,32€ (SD=30,58845; N=142). The ocean plastic alternative was rated a bit higher with a mean of 63,33€ (SD=33,47842; N=142).

c) Relation between WTP Statements

The Pearson Correlation was conducted on all four WTP statements in order to understand in which way they are related with each other. The results show that the relationship within product categories is stronger than between product categories.

Hence, participants who indicated a higher price for sunglasses from recycled plastic also indicated a higher price for sunglasses from ocean plastic ($r=,823$ (significant at a 0.01 level); $p=,000$). The same principle is applicable for the FMCG ($r=,893$ (significant at a 0.01 level); $p=,000$).

Between product categories the correlation coefficients were visibly smaller ranging between $r=,293$ and $r=420$ (significant at a 0.01 level; $p=,000$), indicating that there is a weaker, but still moderately positive correlation. Therefore, many, but not all participants indicating a higher WTP for a luxury good also indicated a higher WTP for a FMCG and vice versa.

d) Gender Analysis

As females are overrepresented in this study, a glance at the differences in gender is necessary in order to understand how the results are skewed. As too little counts for an item in the survey can harm the validity of the analysis, the 0,06% of diverse people were excluded from this gender analysis. For factors like income, the frequency of purchase of luxury goods and FMCG as well as attitudes like the environmental concern and knowledge the Chi Square Analysis found no significant differences.

Also, product specific items like the perception of contamination for all four products presented in the study, the importance of the brand’s reputation, trust and the ranking of likeliness to buy for the four products did not significantly differentiate between gender. In many cases single significances between gender and an item of the survey were detected. However, significances were too scattered amongst the Likert degrees, which made a conclusive interpretation unfeasible. Hence, only a few factors showed overall interpretable results. These were notably the variables attitude, quality perception, relative benefit perception and WTP.

Overall, women showed a higher degree of positive attitude towards both recycled and ocean plastic. The same pattern is reflected in the perception of relative benefit of the two plastic types in comparison to virgin plastics material. Furthermore, quality perception was rated higher for all four product types by women. Women therefore value the two materials higher than men and expect the products to be of a better quality than their male counterparts. The WTP did not show significant differences concerning the luxury products, but a divergence of 16 and 21 Cents was provable for FMCG of recycled and ocean plastic respectively. The Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney-Test supported the means of Table 1 with significant coefficients. This proves that both plastic types have been monetarily valued higher by women than men.

	WTP in €	
	Female	Male
FMCG		
Recycled Plastic	4,48	4,32
Ocean Plastic	4,68	4,47

Furthermore, the Chi-Square analysis showed that there exists no relation between gender and the not willing to pay more statements. Therefore, the only detectable gender difference in WTP for both plastic types is within the FMCG category.

During the focus group discussions, pragmatism and a higher brand- or product loyalty was stated to be the main reason for the lower WTP for FMCG of males in the survey. Men are

perceived as more practical consumers that are not prone to testing novelties, especially of the cosmetics industry, in comparison to females. A practical and non-explorative approach to purchasing FMCG was therefore indicated as a barrier to test new products.